

**A revision of the taxonomic structure
of *Dorcadion cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787) (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract. *Dorcadion cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787) distributed in Moldova, Ukraine, Russia and Azerbaijan consists of 17 subspecies: *D. c. cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787) - European Russia, central and eastern Ukraine, *D. c. deniz* ssp. nov. - East Azerbaijan, Baku environs, *D. c. napolovi* ssp. nov. - north Azerbaijan, Shemakha environs, *D. c. belousovi* ssp. nov. - north-east Azerbaijan, Velvelichay River, *D. c. terkense* ssp. nov. - Chechnya, Groznyi environs, *D. c. sindorum* ssp. nov. - Russia, Black Sea Coast, Anapa environs, *D. c. veniamini* ssp. nov. - Russia, north-west Caucasus, Markotkh Ridge, *D. c. adygorum* ssp. nov. - Adygeya, Maykop environs, *D. c. smetanai* ssp. nov. - Karachay-Cherkessia, Khasaut environs and Kabardino-Balkaria, Baksan environs, *D. c. macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932, new rank - Ukraine, Kharkov Region, *D. c. skrylniki* ssp. nov. - south-east Ukraine, Melitopol environs, *D. c. azovense* ssp. nov. - south-east Ukraine, Berdiansk environs, *D. c. gorodinskii* Danilevsky, 1996 south Ukraine, Kherson Region, *D. c. perroudi* Pic, 1942, new rank - south-west Crimea, *D. c. bartenevi* ssp. nov. - west Crimea, Tarkhankut Cape, *D. c. panticapaeum* Plavilstshikov, 1951 - north-east Crimea and south-west Russia, Taman Peninsula, *D. c. zubovi* ssp. nov. - Moldova.

INTRODUCTION

Dorcadion cinerarium (Fabricius, 1787) is one of the most common and widely distributed species of the genus, occupying the territories of the whole Ukraine and Moldova republics, as well as south of Russia and north-east Azerbaijan. The species is strongly variable geographically, but most of its geographical forms were not named up to now, or just contrary, were accepted as another species.

Transcaucasian group of species close to *D. cinerarium* was recently revised (Lazarev 2009; 2010).

The data of labels written before 1918 are shown here in original way according to Julian calendar. The modern data (according to Grigorian calendar) differ by 13 days. For example 1st of February by Julian calendar after 31st of January 1918 is 14 of February.

ABBREVIATIONS

Several abbreviations used in the text:

- AB collection of A. Bartenev, Kharkov (Ukraine);
AN collection of A. Napolov, Riga (Latvia);

- AS collection of A. Shapovalov, Orenburg (Russia);
 ArS collection of A. Shekhovtsov, Kharkov (Ukraine);
 AZ collection of A. Zubov, Kishenev (Moldova);
 DK collection of D. Kasatkin, Rostov-on-Don (Russia);
 MD collection of M. Danilevsky, Moscow (Russia);
 ML collection of M. Lazarev, Moscow (Russia);
 MS collection of M. Smirnov, Ivanovo (Russia);
 OP collection of O. Pak, Donetsk (Ukraine);
 YuS collection of Yu. Skrylnik, Kharkov (Ukraine);
 MPSU Moscow Pedagogical State University, Moscow (Russia);
 ZIN Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences, Sankt-Petersburg (Russia);
 ZMM Zoological Museum of Moscow State University, Moscow (Russia).

General distribution is described for each taxon with a list of all known localities. Each locality name is followed by the reference to corresponding publication in brackets or/and by the abbreviation of the collection, where material with corresponding label is preserved.

RESULTS

Taxonomy structure of *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787)

I. *Dorcadion cinerarium cinerarium*-group of subspecies

1. ssp. *cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787)
2. ssp. *macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932, new rank
3. ssp. *perroudi* Pic, 1942, new rank
4. ssp. *zubovi* ssp. nov.
5. ssp. *veniamini* ssp. nov.
6. ssp. *adygorum* ssp. nov.
7. ssp. *terkense* ssp. nov.
8. ssp. *deniz* ssp. nov.
9. ssp. *napolovi* ssp. nov.
10. ssp. *belousovi* ssp. nov.

II. *Dorcadion cinerarium panticapaeum*-group of subspecies

11. ssp. *smetanai* ssp. nov.
12. ssp. *azovense* ssp. nov.
13. ssp. *skrylniki* ssp. nov.
14. ssp. *panticapaeum* Plavilstshikov, 1951
15. ssp. *sindorum* ssp. nov.
16. ssp. *bartenevi* ssp. nov.
17. ssp. *gorodinskii* Danilevsky, 1996

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787)**
(Figs 1-63, Photo 1-7, Maps 1-2)

Lamia cineraria Fabricius, 1787: 140 („Pallas Icon. tab. F. fig 11. Habitat in Russia meridionali“).

Type locality. East Ukraine and south of European Russia (Lazarev 2009).

Dorcadion cinerarium (Fabricius, 1787) was described as *Lamia cineraria* Fabricius, 1787 (Fig. 1). The description was based on a female and a picture of a female.

The syntype female (Fig. 3) from collection of Fabricius is preserved now in the collection of Universitetes Zoologiske Museum, København (before in Kiel, Germany). It has two labels: one by Fabricius hand “*cineraria*” (Fig. 4) and second printed: “Kiel II. 300.102”, usual form for Fabricius type materials. The female does not belong to the species, which is generally accepted as *D. cinerarium*, but to *D. pusillum* Küster, 1847b, which is also widely distributed in southern Ukraine and south-western Russia.

Second syntype - a female (Fig. 2) figured by Pallas (1781) without locality (in fact without any text at all) can be attributed to the species which is known now as *D. cinerarium*.

***cineraria*. 45. L. thorace spinoso cinerascens, antennis breuibus,
Pallas Icon. tab. F. fig. 11.
Habitat in Russia meridionali Dom. Hybner.
Statura et summa affinitas praecedentis, at duplo fere
minor et totum corpus cinerascens.**

1

Figs 1-4. 1- Original description of *Lamia cineraria* Fabricius, 1787; 2- Picture (Pallas, 1771) of *Lamia cineraria* F. (female, lectotype); 3- *Dorcadion pusillum tanaiticum*, female, paralectotype of *Lamia cineraria* F.; 4- The unique label of the paralectotype of *Lamia cineraria* F.

Map 1. The whole area of *D. cinerarium*. *D. c. cinerarium*-group of subspecies - red symbols; *D. c. panticapaeum*-group of subspecies - blue symbols. *D. c. cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787) (Russia: Kursk Region: 1, Belgorod Region: 2-4, Voronezh Region: 5-19, Volgograd Region: 20-25, Samara Region: 26, Rostov Region: 27-37, Krasnodar Region: 38-40, Ukraine: Zhitomir Region: 41, Kiev Region: 42, Odessa Region: 43-44, Kirovograd Region: 45, Dnepropetrovsk Region: 46-48, Poltava Region: 49-50, Kharkov Region: 51-54, Lugansk Region: 55-61, Donetsk Region: 62-79, Nikolaev Region: 80-81, Zaporozhye Region: 82), *D. c. veniamini* ssp. nov. (Russia: Krasnodar Region: 83), *D. c. adygorum* ssp. nov. (Russia: Adygeya Republic: 84), *D. c. terkense* ssp. nov. (Russia: Chechnya: 85), *D. c. zubovi* ssp.n. (Moldova: 86-90), *D. c. belousovi* ssp. nov. (Azerbaijan: 91), *D. c. napolovi* ssp. nov. (Azerbaijan: 92-94), *D. c. napolovi* ssp. nov. *D. c. deniz* ssp. nov. (Azerbaijan: 95), *D. c. macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932 (Ukraine: Kharkov Region: 96-102), *D. c. perroudi* Pic, 1942, new rank (Map 2; Crimea), *D. c. gorodinskii* Danilevsky, 1996 (Moldova: 103, Ukraine: Odessa Region: 104-105, Nikolaevsky Region: 106-108, Kherson Region: 109-111, Zaporozhye Region: 112-113), *D. c. skrylniki* ssp. nov. (Ukraine: Melitopol Region: 114-115), *D. c. azovense* ssp. nov. (Ukraine: Zaporozhye Region: 116), *D. c. bartenevi* ssp. nov. (Ukraine: Crimea: 117), *D. c. panticapaeum* Plavilstshikov, 1951 (Ukraine: Crimea: 118, 120-129, Kherson Region: 119, Russia: Krasnodar Region: 130-131), *D. c. sindorum* ssp. nov. (Russia: Krasnodar Region: 132), *D. c. smetanai* ssp. nov. (Russia: Karachay-Cherkessia Republic: 133, Kabardino-Balkar Republic: 134).

1 - Kursk Region, 2 - Belgorod District [south environs of Belgorod city], 3 - Novyi Oskol District, [1km northwards Belyi Kolodets, about 50°37'N, 37°19'E], 4 - Veydelevka District, [2,5km southwards Viktoropol, about 50°03'N, 38°28'E], 5 - Voronezh city, 6 - Novovoronezh, 51°19'N, 39°13'E, 7 - Korotoyak, 50°58'N, 39°11'E, 8 - Divnogore, 50°57'N, 39°17'E, 9 - 2km southwards Gniloe, about 50°47'N, 39°04'E, 10 - 30km southwards Ostrogozhsk, about 50°35'N, 39°04'E, 11 - Drozdovo, 50°20'N, 39°23'E, 12 - Rossosh, 50°12'N, 39°35'E, 13 - 20km northwards Rossosh, about 50°22'N, 39°35'E, 14 - Medovo, 49°44'N, 40°42'E, 15 - Belaya Gorka, 49°47'N, 40°57'E, 16 - 4km

That female was designated by Lazarev (2009) as a lectotype of *Lamia cineraria* Fabricius, 1787, so the sense of the name *Dorcadion cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787) was protected. The absence of the corresponding specimen does not prevent the designation of the lectotype (ICZN, Art. 74.4). Another syntype (Fig. 3) from København Museum was designated (Lazarev 2009) as paralectotype.

The type locality of the taxon must be the geographical location of the female figured by Pallas (1781). The picture itself was not followed by any text, so the unique information on the origin of the corresponding material was in the title of the publication «Icones insectorum praesertim Rossiae Sibiriaque peculiarium», with Russia and Siberia mentioned. Similar *Dorcadion* absent in Siberia and known only from southern Russia of XVIII century (modern eastern Ukraine and south of European Russia).

Diagnosis. Body of moderate size, prothorax without spines, but with small obtuse tubercles, pronotum and elytra relatively smooth, elytra in males with only one white stripe (sutural) on dorsal side, marginal white elytral stripes in males also present; elytra in females with rather variable dense pubescence or glabrous; pubescent female elytra usually with wide pale (dirty-white) external dorsal and humeral stripes, internal dorsal pale elytral stripes always absent.

Body in males relatively narrow, frons covered with small distinct punctures, which are not very dense; vertex with moderately dense punctation, fine white pubescence is situated on genae and around eyes; antennae thin, protruding to about apical elytral third, 1st antennal joint usually red, dark-red, or rarely black, densely covered by dirty-white pubescence; other joints nearly always black, or sometimes partly dark-red; prothorax transverse, lateral tubercles wide and obtuse, with rough punctation laterally; pronotum with more or less dense punctation along middle, with white longitudinal line, which sometimes can be totally indistinct; forms with totally pubescent elytra have totally pubescent pronotum; in forms with mostly glabrous elytra pronotum could be sometimes partly or totally covered with black recumbent pubescence; pronotal punctation consists of big dots and microsculpture (very fine dots) in between; scutellum triangular, transverse, sometimes elongated with whitish pubescence; elytra black, usually reddish along lateral and posterior borders, but sometimes totally black, regularly oval, widened near middle, evenly convex with poorly pronounced longitudinal striae; glabrous in most part or densely pubescent; white sutural stripe is always accompanied by black subsutural stripes; sometimes rudiments of humeral white stripes present, specially in totally pubescent elytra; lateral curved elytral margins usually with scattered black recumbent setae even in mostly glabrous elytra; sometimes scattered black setae can be visible on glabrous elytra; humeral carinae obtuse, external dorsal carinae are a little exposed in the first elytral third; internal dorsal carinae obliterated; sometimes several white setae are situated anteriorly along external dorsal furrow; marginal white stripes very narrow, just a little wider than epipleurae; legs red, dark-red or sometimes black, always with more or less dense white pubescence; last abdominal sternite shallowly emarginated, pygidium and postpygidium widely rounded.

Females are similar to males, but body much wider; androchromal females sometimes dominate in the populations, but usually females are mostly autochromal with pubescent elytra (among glabrous males) or with pale elytra (among black or dark-brown males);

westwards Marki, about 50°47'N, 39°36'E, 17 - Nikolo-Varvarinka, 51°00'N, 39°58'E, 18 - Burlyavka, 50°59'N, 41°19'E, 19 - Varvarino, 51°12'N, 41°43'E, 20 - Uryupinsk, 50°48'N, 42°01'E, 21 - Olkhovka, 49°51'N, 44°33'E, 22 - Trekhostrovskaya, 49°05'N, 43°55'E, 23 - Golubinskiy, 48°51'N, 43°33'E, 24 - Kalach-on-Don, 48°41'N, 43°32'E, 25 - Sarepta, 48°31'N, 44°30'E, 26 - Samara enverons, 27 - Millerovo District, Fominka, 49°01'N, 40°35'E, 28 - Kamensk-Shakhtinskiy, 48°19'N, 40°15'E, 29 - Sinegorskiy, 48°00'N, 40°51'E, 30 - Kazachiy Lageri, 47°33'N, 40°07'E, 31 - Novocherkassk, 47°25'N, 40°05'E, 32 - Rostov-on-Don, 33 - Nedvigovka environs, about 47°16'N, 39°20'E, 34 - Margaritovka, 46°55'N, 38°52'E, 35 - Taganrog environs, 36 - Efremovka, 47°19'N, 38°29'E, 37 - Avilo-Uspenska, 47°41'N, 38°40'E, 38 - Shkurinskaya, 46°35'N, 39°21'E, 39 - Mingrelskaya, 45°00'N, 38°20'E, 40 - Pashkovskiy, 45°02'N, 39°05'E, 41 - Zhitomir, 42 - Kiev environs, 43 - Balta, 47°56'N, 29°37'E, 44 - Ananev District, Dolinskoe, 47°32'N, 29°55'E, 45 - Kirovograd, 46 - Tokovskoe, 47°39'N, 33°57'E, 47 - Nikopol environs, about 47°34'N, 34°23'E, 48 - Pavlograd, 48°31'N, 35°52'E, 49 - Mirgorod District, Yareski, 49°50'N, 33°54'E, 50 - Poltava, 51 - Krasnograd, 49°22'N, 35°27'E, 52 - Volchansk, 50°17'N, 36°56'E, 53 - Volchansk District, Oktyabrskoe Forestry, 50°20'N, 37°10'E, 54 - Volchansk District, Okhrimovka, 50°20'N, 37°12'E, 55 - between Kupyansk, 49°42'N, 37°37'E and Svatovo, 49°24'N, 38°09', 56 - Derkul, 49°16'N, 39°39'E, 57 - Melovoy District, Luganskiy Natural Reserve, Streltsovskaya Step, about 49°17'N, 40°04'E, 58 - Stanichno-Luganskoe District, Luganskiy Natural Reserve, Pridonetsovskaya Poyma, about 48°44'N, 39°22'E, 59 - Sverdlovsk District, Luganskiy Natural Reserve, Provalskaya Step, about 48°07'N, 39°49'E (Kalininskiy), 60 - Sverdlovsk District, Provale environs, about 48°07'N, 39°48'E, 61 - Sverdlovsk District, Luganskiy Natural Reserve, Provalskaya Step, about 48°08'N, 39°53'E (Grushevskiy), 62 - Krasnyi Liman District, Yatskovka, 49°10'N, 37°32'E, 63 - Tatyankovka, 49°02'N, 37°35'E, 64 - Slovyansk, 48°51'N, 37°36'E, 65 - Dobropole District, Nikanorovka, 48°25'N, 37°15'E, 66 - Konstantinovka District, Stepanovka, 48°27'N, 37°36'E, 67 - Marinka District, Karlovka environs, about 48°06'N, 37°29'E, 68 - Donetsk, 69 - Artemovsk, 48°36'N, 38°00'E, 70 - Konstantinovka District, Kurdyumovka, 48°28'N, 37°57'E, 71 - Gorlovka, 48°18'N, 38°03'E, 72 - Yasinovataya District, Verkhnetoretskoe, 48°13'N, 37°52'E, 73 - Shakhtersk, 48°02'N, 38°29'E, 74 - Starobeshevo environs, about 47°45'N, 38°02'E, 75 - Novoazovsk District, Khomutovo, 47°15'N, 38°08'E, 76 - Shakhterskoe District, Donetskii Kryazh, 47°52'N, 38°24'E, 77 - Volodaskoe District, Kamennye Mogily Natural Reserve, 47°18'N, 37°04'E, 78 - Pershotravnevoe District, Yalta, 46°58'N, 37°16'E, 79 - Shirokino, 47°05'N, 37°48'E, 80 - Pervomayskiy District, Migiya [48°02'N, 30°56'E], Yuzhny Bug River, 81 - Pervomayskiy District, Kuripchino [48°00'N, 31°00'E], Yuzhny Bug River, 82 - Zaporozhye, 83 - Novorossiysk environs, Andreevsky Pass, 44°43'N 37°52'E, 84 - Maykop environs, 85 - Groznyi environs, 86 - Korneshty, 47°21'N, 28°00'E, 87 - Kishinev, 88 - Leova District, between Kyzlyar, 46°38'N, 28°31'E and Knyazevka, 46°37'N, 28°28'E, 89 - Rezeny, 46°45'N, 28°53'E, 90 - Bendery, 46°49'N, 29°28'E, 91 - Kuba District, Velvelichay River, about 41°13'N, 48°38'E, 92 - Demerchi, 40°50'N, 48°33'E, 93 - Shemakha environs, Pirkuli Natural Reserve, about 40°46'N, 48°32'E, 94 - Shemakha environs, 40°38'N, 48°38'E, 95 - Baku enverons, 96 - Zolochev District, 1-2 km N Dolzhik village, 50°11'N 35°58'E, 97 - Kharkov environs, 98 - Dokuchaev, 49°54'N 36°26'E, 99 - Novaya Vodolaga, 49°43'N 35°52'E, 100 - Izyum environs, 49°13'N 37°17'E, 101 - Chervonyi Shakhter, Pridonetskoe Forestry, 49°11'N 37°03'E, 102 - Izyum District, Malaya Kamyshevakha, 49°06'N 37°13'E, 103 - Purkary [46°32'N, 29°51'E], 104 - Khadzhibeevskiy Liman, 46°51'N, 30°28'E, 105 - Odessa environs, 106 - Nikolaev environs, 107 - Nikolaev District, Staraya Bogdanovka environs [46°50'N, 31°54'E], Dnepr-Bug Liman, 108 - Nikolaev District, Parutino, 109 - Belozerka District, Znamenka, 46°42'N, 32°23'E, 110 - Darevka near Kherson-city, 111 - Rybalche, 112 - Kamenka Dnepropetrovskaya [47°29'N, 34°23'E], 113 - Khortitsa Island [47°49'N, 35°05'E], 114 - 2 km E Novoe, 5 km SW Melitopol, 46°47'N, 35°18'E, 115 - Molochnyi Liman, about 46°41'N, 35°19'E, 116 - Berdyansk environs, 117 - Tarkhankut Cape, 118 - Turetsky Val (Perekop Isthmus), about 46°08'N, 33°41'E, 119 - Chongar Peninsula, 120 - Dzhanqoy, 45°42'N, 34°23'E, 121 - Uytumoe, 45°31'N, 34°35'E, 122 - Oktyabr, Pyatikhatka River [45°19'N, 34°16'E], 123 - Kazantip Cape, 124 - Mysovoe, 45°26'55.41"N, 35°50'27.66"E, 125 - 10 km westwards Fontan, about 45°15'N, 35°53'E, 126 - Shchelkino [20-25 km eastwards Kazantip Cape], 127 - Bagerovo, 45°22'N, 36°17'E, 128 - Kerch environs, 45°20'N, 36°28'E, 129 - Mitridat Mountain, 45°20'54"N, 36°28'02"E, 130 - Taman enverons, 131 - Karabetova Mountain [45°12'02"N, 36°46'51"E], 132 - Anapa environs, 133 - Khasaut environs, 43°42'N, 42°30'E, 134 - Baksan environs, 43°41'N, 43°31'E

Map 2. The Crimean part of the area of *D. cinerarium*. *D. c. cinerarium*-group of subspecies - red symbols; *D. c. panticaepeum*-group of subspecies - blue symbols *D. c. perroudi* Pic, 1942, new rank (Crimea: 1-38), *D. c. panticaepeum* Plavilstshikov, 1951 (Crimea: 39-49, Krasnodar Region: 50-51, Kherson Region: 52), *D. c. bartenevi* ssp. nov. (Crimea: 53).

1 - Natashino, 45°24'N, 33°16'E, 2 - Sevastopol, 44°36'N, 33°32'E, 3 - Inkerman, 44°36'N, 33°36'E, 4 - Balaklava, 44°30'N, 33°36'E, 5 - Laspi, 44°25'N, 33°43'E, 6 - Orlineo, 44°26'N, 33°46'E, 7 - Foros, 44°23'N, 33°47'E, 8 - Parkovoe, 44°24'N, 33°54'E, 9 - Simeiz, 44°24'N, 33°59'E, 10 - Alupka, 44°25'N, 34°02'E, 11 - Miskhor, 44°25'N, 34°05'E, 12 - Gaspra, 44°25'N, 34°06'E, 13 - Koreiz, 44°25'N, 34°05'E, 14 - Yalta, 44°29'N, 34°09'E, 15 - Yaltinskaya-Yayla, 44°33'N, 34°08'E, 16 - Gurzuf, 44°33'N, 34°17'E, 17 - Zaprudnoe, 44°35'N, 34°19', 18 - Alushta, 44°40'N, 34°24'E, 19 - Verkhnyaya Kutuzovka, 44°43'N, 34°22'E, 20 - South Demerdzhi Mountain, 44°44'N, 34°23'E, 21 - Luchistoe, 44°44'N, 34°24'E, 22 - Angarskiy Pass, 44°45'N, 34°20'E, 23 - Chatyr-Dag, 44°46'N, 34°17'E, 24 - North Demerdzhi Mountain, 44°46'N, 34°23'E, 25 - Krasnopeschchernaya, 44°51'N, 34°20'E, 26 - Marino, 44°55'N, 34°08'E, 27 - Lozovoe, 44°54'N, 34°09'E, 28 - Dubki, 44°56'N, 34°01'E, 29 - Simferopol, 44°56'N, 34°06'E, 30 - Kamenka, 44°59'N, 34°10'E, 31 - Sudak, 44°51'N, 34°58'E, 32 - Kurskoe, 45°01'N, 34°56'E, 33 - Agarmysh Mountain, 45°02'N, 35°02'E, 34 - Staryi Krym, 45°01'N, 35°05'E, 35 - Shchebetovka, 44°56'N, 35°09'E, 36 - Karadag Mountain, 44°55'N, 35°13'E, 37 - Feodosiya, 45°02'N, 35°22'E, 38 - Vladislavovka, 45°09'N, 35°22'E; 39 - Turetsky Val (Perekop Isthmus), about 46°08'N, 33°41'E, 40 - Dzhankoy, 45°42'N, 34°23'E, 41 - Uyutnoe, 45°31'N, 34°35'E, 42 - Oktyabr, Pyatikhatka River [45°19'N, 34°16'E], 43 - Kazantip Cape, 44 - Mysovoe, 45°26'55.41"N, 35°50'27.66"E, 45 - 10 km westwards Fontan, about 45°15'N, 35°53'E, 46 - Shchelkino [20-25 km eastwards Kazantip Cape], 47 - Bagerovo, 45°22'N, 36°17'E, 48 - Kerch environs, 45°20'N, 36°28'E, 49 - Mitridat Mountain, 45°20'54"N, 36°28'02"E, 50 - Taman environs, 51 - Karabetova Mountain [45°12'02"N, 36°46'51"E], 52 - Chongar Peninsula, 53 - Tarkhankut Cape.

antennae usually protruding to about elytral middle; elytral furrows deeper than in males; elytral carinae better developed; humeral elytral pale stripes (if present) usually wider than dorsal stripes (if present), and much wider than white sutural stripe; last abdominal sternite widely rounded with a small depression in the middle, last tergite narrowly rounded.

Microspecules; central trunk (ct) without ventral tubercle, hardly delimited from central bladder, densely covered. Aedeagus (Lazarev 2009) distinctly sharpened; endophallus (Fig.

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Figs 5-13. *D. c. cinerarium*: 5- Endophallus of *D. c. cinerarium*, Rostov, Krasnyi Sulin District, ab - apical bulb, ae - aedeagus, af - apical furrow, ap - apical phallomer, bb - apical bubble, bp - basal phallomer, bt - basal tube, cb - central bladder, ct - central trunk, mt - medial tube, pb - preapical bulb, vp - plates; 6- male, Rostov; 7- female, Rostov Region, Sinegorskiy; 8- male, Voronezh Region. 9- female, Voronezh Region, Divnogore; 10- male, Zhitomir; 11- female, same locality; 12- male, Kharkov Region, Okhrimovka; 13- female, Kharkov Region, Volchansk District, Oktyabrskoe Forestry.

5) relatively long and narrow, but shorter than body; basal tube (bt) strongly attenuated, straight, transversally rugose; ventral plates (vp) small; medial tube (mt) long and narrow with distinct dilation at middle; central bladder (cb) poorly developed, partly covered with very short microspecules; preapical bulb (pb) small, elongated; apical bulb (ab) narrow, cylindrical.

Body length in males: 8.7-15.5 mm, in females: 9.3-16.1 mm; body width in males: 3.1-5.6 mm, in females: 4.1-6.5 mm.

Distribution. *D. cinerarium* is distributed from Voronezh Region of Russia in the north to Moldova in the west, to the North Caucasus in south-west and Azerbaijan in south-east; the eastern border of the species area in Europe is in general Volga River (the labels "Samara" of two very old males are rather doubtful). Western border of the area is about same as the western state border of Moldova - Prut River. The most southern populations are distributed from Taman Peninsula to Anapa environs, then to North-West Caucasus (Novorossiysk), Adygeya and Chechnya and then to north Azerbaijan. The records of *D. cinerarium* for Karachaevo-Cherkesia (Daut Canyon) by D. Kasatkin & Yu. Arzanov (1997) was connected with *D. sareptanum striatiforme* Suvorov, 1913.

Dense populations of *D. cinerarium* are known from many regions of South Russia, Moldova and Ukraine; the species is very common in Crimea.

Many *Dorcadion* populations from Turkey and North Iran were wrongly traditionally regarded as forms of *D. cinerarium* or *D. micans* Thomson, 1867, *D. sericatum* Kraatz, 1873a, *D. macropus* Kraatz, 1873b. In fact the species a little penetrates southwards Caucasian Ridge only in north-east Azerbaijan and is absent in other parts of Transcaucasia. All populations from Iran and Turkey (Breuning 1962; Özdikmen 2010), which are up to now regarded as *D. cinerarium* (often as subspecies, variations, morphs, forms or aberrations) belong to another partly undescribed species, which differ by the details of integument sculpture, shape and size of body, genital structures and usually by the domination of glabrous females, that is not typical for *D. cinerarium*.

According to Plavilstshikov (1952) the area of the species (as "*D. caucasicum*") occupies the whole Caucasus from Don steppe areas and Ciscaucasia to Transcaucasia. Still there are no specimens of *D. cinerarium* from Georgia or Armenia in Plavilstshikov's collection, as well as in the collection of Zoological Institute (St.-Petersburg). Specimens of *D. sulcipenne* Küster, 1847a from Tbilisi environs without pubescence (so *D. sulcipenne caucasicum* Küster, 1847c - see Lazarev 2009) were identified by Plavilstshikov as "*D. caucasicum*". A part of glabrous specimens from near Tbilisi (mostly females) were identified by him as *D. sulcipenne* m. *exsertum*, and another part (mostly males) as *D. caucasicum*. The typical *D. sulcipenne* from Tbilisi environs (so *D. sulcipenne sulcipenne* Küster, 1847a - see Lazarev 2009) is densely covered with black pubescence. Just that pair of forms was originally described as two different species *D. sulcipenne* Küster, 1847a and *D. caucasicum* Küster, 1847c.

The real nature of *D. caucasicum* as a glabrous form of *D. sulcipenne* is quite evident from the original descriptions because of well developed lateral thoracic spines (impossible in *D. cinerarium*) and longitudinal elytral furrows - the most important character of *D. sulcipenne*, so *D. sulcipenne* Küster, 1847a = *D. caucasicum* Küster, 1847c (Lazarev 2009).

Before Danilevsky et al. (2005) conditionally accepted the name *D. cinerarium caucasicum* Küster, 1847c for several Caucasian populations of different species of “group-cinerarium” recently described as *D. sisianense* Lazarev, 2009, *D. megriense* Lazarev, 2009 and *D. shushense* Lazarev, 2010.

D. s. sulcipenne and *D. s. caucasicum* are separated by Kura River near Tbilisi. *D. s. sulcipenne* is distributed along left (north-east) bank of Kura from about Gldani to Rustavi, while *D. s. caucasicum* is distributed along right (south-west) bank of the Kura from about Digomi to Tskhneti. So, numerous pubescent specimens (*D. s. sulcipenne*) with the label “Tbilisi” preserved in different museums were collected north-eastwards from the city.

The species includes 17 subspecies which could be delimited in two groups: the „*Dorcadion cinerarium cinerarium*-group“ of subspecies consists of populations with glabrous males: most of males in each population with shining glabrous elytra, only sutural, subsutural and marginal setae stripes present. Males of the „*Dorcadion cinerarium panticapaeum*-group“ of subspecies have totally pubescent elytra.

I. „*Dorcadion cinerarium cinerarium*-group“

Most of males in each population with shining glabrous elytra, only sutural, subsutural and marginal setae stripes present. Only a few males with totally pubescent elytra are known in certain populations. Elytral pubescence of females is rather different in different populations. Usually elytra are covered with very dense differently coloured setae, or elytral setae more or less sparse and predominantly dark, or elytra are totally glabrous with only sutural, subsutural and marginal setae stripes present.

10 subspecies are accepted here.

1. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787)

(Figs 5-13, Photo 1-2)

Lamia cineraria Fabricius, 1787: 140 („Pallas Icon. tab. F. fig 11. Habitat in Russia meridionali“).

Lamia tricolor Fischer-Waldheim, 1805: 15 („les environs de Moscou, et du Wolga“).

Dorcadion sericatum, Krynicki, 1832: 160, part; Sturm, 1843: 260.

Dorcadion cinerarium, Küster, 1848: 78; Thomson, 1867: 66, part; Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997: 64; Kaliuzhnaya et al., 2000: 185.

Dorcadion (s. str.) *caucasicum*, Aurivillius, 1922: 41, part.; Winkler, 1929: 1192, part.; Oglöblin, 1948: 466 (south of European Russia eastwards Dnepr River).

Dorcadion (s. str.) *cinerarium*, Aurivillius, 1922: 42, part.

Dorcadion caucasicum, Sturm, 1843: 260, nomen nudum; Küster, 1847c: 98; Plavilstshikov, 1927a: 5; 1927b: 51; 1948: 127, part.; Zahaikévitch, 1991: 148; Negrobov et al., 2005: 603; Prisnyi, 2005: 40.

Dorcadion (Compsodorcadion) caucasicum, Plavilstshikov, 1932b: 193, part.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium, Breuning, 1946: 117, part.; 1962: 361, part.; Danilevsky, 1996: 66, part.; Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 32 part.

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) caucasicum, Plavilstshikov, 1958: 118, part.; 1965: 411, part; Lobanov et al., 1982: 263, part.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium morpha *caucasicum*, Breuning, 1962: 361, part. („Ukraine, Krim, Westkaukasus, Nord-Anatolien“)

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium morpha ♀ *subobesum*, Breuning, 1962: 363, part. („Ukraine, Nord-Anatolien“).

Photos. 1-2. *D. c. cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787): 1- Volgograd Region, Kumylga River, 140 m, 50°19' N, 42°51' E, 30.04.2009 (Photo by M. Danilevsky); 2- Kharkov Region, Volchansk District, Okhrimovka, (Photo by A. Shekhovtsov).

Figs 14-19. *D. c. macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932, (Kharkov Region): 14- Holotype, male, Izyum; 15- male, Izyum District, Malaya Kamyshevakha; 16- male, 1 km N Aeroport; 17- male, Dokuchaevo, 3 km W Rogan, 49°54'N 36°26'E. 18-19 - female, same locality.

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) cinerarium, Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 329, part; Martynov & Pisarenko: 2004: 60.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium cinerarium, Danilevsky, 1996: 418; Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 33 part.; Bartenev, 2004: 37 part.; 2009: 300 part.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium, Özdikmen, 2007: 296, part.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium cinerarium, Danilevsky et al., 2005: 137, 142, part.; 2010a: 245.

Type locality. Ukraine and south part of European Russia (see above).

Material examined. Russia: 1 ♀, Kursk reg. - ZMM; 2 ♂♂, Samara, Dr. Bolz - ZIN; 1 ♀, Volgograd reg., Sarepta, Khristoforov - ZIN; 1 ♂, Rostov reg., Margaritovka - ZIN; 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, Don, Novocherkassk, iv.1917 - ZMM; 1 ♂, Rostov-na-Donu, 08.v.1922 - ZMM; 2 ♂♂, Volgograd reg., Koper River, Uryupinsk, 30.iii.1929, A. Menstschikov - ZMM; 9 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Krasnodar reg., Mingrelskaya, 05-11.vi.1930, Galkin - ZMM; 3 ♂♂, Rostov reg., Kamensk [now Kamensk-Shakhtinskiy], 23.iv.1950, K.Arnoldi - MPSU; 1 ♀, Rostov reg., Sinegorskiy, 07.v.1972, Lunina - MD; 1 ♀, Don, Novocherkassk ot Aksay, 22.iv.1975 - ZMM; 1 ♂, Voronezh reg., 20 km N Rossosh, 13.v.1980, Anosov - MD; 1 ♀, 75 km S Voronezh, Divnogore, 06.v.1984 - MD; 1 ♀, Krasnodar reg., Pashkovskaya [now Pashkovskiy], 09.v.1988, E.Stepanov - ZIN; 1 ♀, 30 km W Rostova-na-Donu, Nedvigovka, 24.v.1989, A.Naplov - AN; 1 ♂, Voronezh reg., 30 km S Ostrogozhsk 24.iv.1997, Tsurikov - MD; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Volgograd reg., Olkhovka, 17.v.1997, V.Sychev - MD; 5 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Rostov reg., Krasnyi Sulin District, v.2001, D.Kasatkin - ML; 4 ♂♂, Volgograd reg., Novoanensk District, 27 km SSE Novoanensk, Kumylga River, 27.iv.2008, M.Smironov - MS; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Volgograd reg., Kumylga River, 140 m, 50°19' N, 42°51' E, 30.iv.2009, M.Danilevsky - MD; 20 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀, Rostov, 01-04.v.2009, Yu.G.Arzanov - MD. Ukraine: 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Kiev - ZIN; 1 ♀, Donetsk reg., Bakhmut [now Artemovsk], 06.iv.1892 - ZIN; 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Donetsk reg., Slovyansk, 26.iv.1896, Sokolov - ZMM; 1 ♂, Donetsk reg., Bakhmut [now Artemovsk], 30.iv.1908, Valch. - ZMM; 1 ♂, Poltava, 12.iv.1912, Ogloblin - ZMM; 1 ♂, Poltava reg., Mirgorod District, Yareski 27.v.1919 - ZMM; 1 ♀, Kharkov reg., Krasnograd, 1926, F. Lukyanovich - ZMM; 1 ♂, Voroshilovgrad [now Lugansk] reg., Derkul, 22.iv.1934, A.Alekseev - ZMM; 1 ♂, Svyatogorsk, Tatyankovka, 17.v.1937, Arnoldi - ZIN; 3 ♂♂, 8 ♀♀, Kirovograd, 05.v.1946 - ZMM, ZIN; 1 ♂, Odessa reg, Balta, 01.vi.1948, I.Maltsev - AB; 4 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, Zhitomir, vi.1949, S.Nikereev - MD; 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Voroshilovgrad [now Lugansk] reg., between Kupyansk and Svatovo, 23.iv.1954, G. Mazokhin - ZMM; 17 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀, Voroshilovgrad [now Lugansk] reg., Derkul, Yunitsa, 27.iv.1954, G. Mazokhin - ZMM; 1 ♂, Natural Reserve, Streltsovskaya Step, 06.vi.1971 - AB; 2 ♂♂, Kharkov reg., Volchansk, 24.iv.1985, Efremov - MPSU; 11 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Kharkov reg., Volchansk District, Efremovskoe Forestry [now Oktyabrskoe Forestry], [Okhrimovka environs], 24.iv.1985, I.Plyushch - MD; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Dnepropetrovsk reg., Nikopol environs, 10.v.-20.vi.1987, Tretyakov - AN; 1 ♂, Donetsk reg., 12 km E Mariupol, Shirokino, 29.iv.1990, I.Blonskiy - MPSU; 7 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, Dnepropetrovsk reg, Pavlograd, 01-15.v.1993, V.Brigadirenko - MD, AN; 1 ♂, Donetsk reg., Shakhtersk, 15.v.1995 - AB; 11 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀, Dnepropetrovsk reg., Apostolovo District, Tokovskoe, 19.iv.1998, 30.iv.1998, 19.v.1998, 26.iv.2000 - MPSU, ML; 4 ♂♂, Odessa reg., Ananiv District, Dolinskoe, 02-03.iv.2002, S.Vashchenko - MD; 5 ♂♂ (including 2 totally pubescent males), Zaporozhye, 5-10.05.2008, S.Alekseenko - ArS, ML; 15 ♂♂, Donetsk, Botanical garden, 15-28.iv.2009, A.Gubin - OP; 1 ♂, Kharkov reg., Volchansk District, Efremovka [now Okhrimovka], 23.v.2010, A.Shekhovtsov - ArS; 2 ♂♂, Kharkov reg., Volchansk District, Okhrimovka, 50°20'59.29"N, 37°13'29.49"E, h=140m, 25.v.2010, Yu.Skrylnik, A. Dronov - YuS.

Diagnosis. Body moderately big; antennae black with 1st joint usually dark-red or nearly black; prothorax lateral tubercles shortly angulated; pronotal longitudinal furrow usually interrupted near middle by small convexity; pronotal longitudinal stripes in males very narrow and sometimes not complete; pronotum in males with sparse big dots (often rather scattered) and fine dense punctation; male pronotum sometimes with scattered black recumbent setae, which very rare can be rather dense (males from Samara); males are always with mostly glabrous elytra (two males with totally pubescent elytra are known from near Zaporozhye, but the local population is regarded here as transitional to *D. c. gorodinskii*, because others males here are typically glabrous); scattered recumbent setae in glabrous elytral area always absent; females are always autochromal with densely pubescent pale-brown (usually), dark-

brown or nearly black elytra; dirty-white dorsal elytral stripes in females always present, but sometimes rather narrow, diffused and nearly indistinct, sometimes interrupted by black spots; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) nearly indistinct; anterior part of humeral area with dense big dots disappearing before middle; fine elytral irregular striae more or less obliterated or hardly visible anteriorly; apical elytral margin usually reddish; legs usually dark-red or nearly black.

Body length in males: 10.0-12.0 mm, in females: 10.9-13.5 mm; body width in males: 3.5-4.5 mm, in females: 4.3-5.6 mm.

D. c. cinerarium is characterized by glabrous males, absence of androchromal females, usually pale colour of female pubescence, dark-red or nearly black 1st antennal joint and legs.

Certain specimens from Kharkov (Volchansk District), Donetsk, Lugansk and Rostov regions have rather dark legs and antennae, so the corresponding populations are transitional to the next subspecies *D. c. macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932.

Distribution. South of European Russia, central and north Ukraine; the eastern border of the area is in general Volga River, but two specimens are available with the label "Samara", so, the taxon seems to be able to penetrate to the eastern Volga bank; western border goes from Zhitomir Region of Ukraine to the north of Odessa Region; the northernmost localities are situated in Kiev, Kursk and Voronezh regions (and possibly in Samara environs); in the south the taxon does not reach the Black Sea coast and Caucasian foothills.

The population from near Zaporozhye is regarded here as transitional to *D. c. gorodinskii*.

Known localities in Russia are - Belgorod Region: Belgorod District [south environs of Belgorod city - private message by Prisnyi, 2008] - (Prisnyi, 2005); Novyi Oskol District, [1 km northwards Belyi Kolodets, about 50°37'N, 37°19'E - private message by Prisnyi, 2008] - (Prisnyi, 2005); Veydelevka District, [2.5 km southwards Viktoropol, about 50°03'N, 38°28'E - private message by Prisnyi, 2008] - (Prisnyi, 2005); Krasnodar Region: Mingrelskaya, 45°00'N, 38°20'E - ZMM; Pashkovskiy, 45°02'N, 39°05'E - ZIN; Shkurinskaya, 46°35'N, 39°21'E - (Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997); Kursk Region - ZMM; Rostov Region: 7 localities (Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997): Avilo-Uspenska, 47°41'N, 38°40'E; Efremovka, 47°19'N, 38°29'E; Millerovo District, Fominka, 49°01'N, 40°35'E; Kazachiy Lageri, 47°33'N, 40°07'E; Nedvigovka environs, about 47°16'N, 39°20'E [and AN]; Rostov-on-Don [and ZMM, MD]; Taganrog environs; Kamensk-Shakhtinskiy, 48°19'N, 40°15'E - MPSU; Krasnyi Sulin District - ML; Margaritovka, 46°55'N, 38°52'E - ZIN; Novocherkassk, 47°25'N, 40°05'E - ZMM; Sinegorskiy, 48°00'N, 40°51'E - MD; Samara Region: Samara environs - ZIN; Volgograd Region: 3 localities (Kaliuzhnaya et al., 2000): Kalach-on-Don, 48°41'N, 43°32'E; Golubinskiy, 48°51'N, 43°33'E; Trekhostrovskaya, 49°05'N, 43°55'E; Olkhovka, 49°51'N, 44°33'E - MD; Kumylga River, left tributary of Khoper - MD, MS; Sarepta, 48°31'N, 44°30'E - ZIN; Uryupinsk, 50°48'N, 42°01'E - ZMM; Voronezh Region: 11 localities in private message by Negrobov, 2008: 4 km westwards Marki, about 50°47'N, 39°36'E; Belaya Gorka, 49°47'N, 40°57'E; Burlyayevka, 50°59'N, 41°19'E; Divnogore [and MD], 50°57'N, 39°17'E; Korotoyak, 50°58'N, 39°11'E; Medovo, 49°44'N, 40°42'E; Nikolo-Varvarinka, 51°00'N, 39°58'E; Novovoronezh, 51°19'N, 39°13'E; Rossosh, 50°12'N,

39°35'E; Varvarino, 51°12'N, 41°43'E; Voronezh city; 2 km southwards Gnilioe, about 50°47'N, 39°04'E - private message by Tsurikov, 2008; 20 km northwards Rossosh, about 50°22'N, 39°35'E - MD; 30 km southwards Ostrogzhsk, about 50°35'N, 39°04'E - MD; Drozdovo, 50°20'N, 39°23'E - private communication by Tsurikov, 2008; Petropavlovka District - (Negrobov et al., 2005).

Known localities in Ukraine are - Dnepropetrovsk Region: Nikopol environs, about 47°34'N, 34°23'E - AN; Pavlograd, 48°31'N, 35°52'E - MD, AN; Tokovskoe, 47°39'N, 33°57'E - MPSU, ML; Donetsk Region: 12 localities (Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004): Dobropole District, Nikanorovka, 48°25'N, 37°15'E; Donetsk [and Bartenev, 2009]; Gorlovka, 48°18'N, 38°03'E; Yasinovataya District, Skotovataya [now Verkhnetoretskoe], 48°13'N, 37°52'E; Konstantinovka District, Kurdyumovka, 48°28'N, 37°57'E; Konstantinovka District, Stepanovka, 48°27'N, 37°36'E; Krasnyi Liman District, Yatskovka, 49°10'N, 37°32'E; Novoazovsk District, Khomutovo, 47°15'N, 38°08'E; Shakhterskoe District, Donetskiy Kryazh, 47°52'N, 38°24'E; Starobeshevo environs, about 47°45'N, 38°02'E; Pershotravnevoe District, Yalta, 46°58'N, 37°16'E; Volodaskoe District, Kamennye Mogily Natural Reserve, 47°18'N, 37°04'E; Artemovsk, 48°36'N, 38°00'E - ZIN, ZMM; Donetsk, Botanical garden - OP; Marinka District, Karlovka environs, about 48°06'N, 37°29'E - (Bartenev, 2009); Shakhtersk, 48°02'N, 38°29'E - AB; Shirokino, 47°05'N, 37°48'E - MPSU; Slovyansk, 48°51'N, 37°36'E - ZMM, ZIN; Tatyankovka, 49°02'N, 37°35'E - ZIN; Kharkov Region: Volchansk District, Oktyabrskoe Forestry, 50°20'N, 37°10'E - MD; Volchansk District, Okhrimovka, 50°20'N, 37°12'E - ArS; Krasnograd, 49°22'N, 35°27'E - ZMM; Volchansk, 50°17'N, 36°56'E - MPSU; Kiev Region: Kiev environs - ZIN; Kirovograd Region: Kirovograd - ZMM, ZIN; Lugansk Region: 3 localities (Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004): Stanichno-Luganskoe District, Luganskiy Natural Reserve, Pridontsovskaya Poyma, about 48°44'N, 39°22'E; Melovoy District, Luganskiy Natural Reserve, Streltsovskaya Step, about 49°17'N, 40°04'E [AB]; Sverdlovsk District, Luganskiy Natural Reserve, Provalskaya Step, about 48°07'N, 39°49'E (Kalininskiy) and 48°08'N, 39°53'E (Grushevskiy); between Kupyansk, 49°42'N, 37°37'E and Svatovo, 49°24'N, 38°09'E - ZMM; Derkul, 49°16'N, 39°39'E - ZMM; Yunitsa - ZMM; Sverdlovsk District, Provale environs, about 48°07'N, 39°48'E - Medvedev, 1950; Nikolaev Region: Pervomayskiy District, Migiya [48°02'N, 30°56'E], Yuzhny Bug River (Bartenev, 2009) Pervomayskiy District, Kuripchino [48°00'N, 31°00'E], Yuzhny Bug River (Bartenev, 2009); Odessa Region: Ananiv District, Dolinskoe, 47°32'N, 29°55'E - MD; Balta, 47°56'N, 29°37'E - AB; Poltava Region: Poltava - ZMM, Mirgorod District, Yareski, 49°50'N, 33°54'E - ZMM; Zaporozhye Region: 5 ♂♂ (including 2 totally pubescent males), Zaporozhye - ArS, ML; Zhitomir Region: Zhitomir - MD.

2. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932, new rank (Figs 14-19, Photo 3)

Dorcadion (s.str.) *caucasicum* var. *macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932a: 183 („Rossia europ.: Ukraina, Izjum (prov. Charkov).”).

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium morpha. *macropoides*, Breuning, 1962: 363 („Charkov“).

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium cinerarium, Bartenev, 2009: 300 part.

Type locality. Ukraine, Kharkov Region, Izyum environs - according to the original description.

Material examined. Holotype, ♂, with 4 labels: 1) „Cotype“ [red], 2) „Rossia mer. Izjum Chark. d. 24.iii.1916“, 3) „*Dorcadion* (s.str.) *caucasicum* Kst. ab. *macropoides* m N. Plavilstshikov det. Typus“, 4) „HOLOTYPUS *Dorcadion caucasicum* var. *MACROPOIDES* det. Plavilstshikov, 1932“ - ZMM; 1 ♂, same locality, 2.v.1924 - MD; 1 ♂, Kharkov, Pomerki, 01.v.1932 - ZMM; 3 ♂♂, Kharkov, 02.v.1936 - ZMM; 3 ♂♂, Kharkov, Novaya Vodolaga, 15.v.1978, A.Bartenev - AB; 1 ♂, Kharkov reg, Izyum District, Pridonetskoe Forestry, 19.v.1987, Vedmederya - AB; 1 ♂, Kharkov environs, 06.vi.2004, V.Terekhova - AB; 5 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, Ukraine, Kharkov reg., Kharkov District, Dokuchaevu environs, 12.iv.2007, 19.iv.2007, 19-20.iv.2007, 04.v.2008, Yu. Skrylnik leg. - MD; 19 ♂♂, 12 ♀♀, Kharkov reg., Dokuchaevu, 3 km W Rogan, 49°54'N 36°26'E, 20.iv.2005, 18.iv.2009, 20.iv.2009, 27.iv.2009, 02.v.2009, Yu. & V. Skrylnik leg. - YuS; 112 ♂♂, 38 ♀♀, same locality, 12.iv.2007, 01.v.2007, 12.04.2009, 15.04.2009, 17.04.2009, Yu. Skrylnik leg. - MD, YuS; 1 ♂, same locality, 20.04.2007, D. Kovalchuk - YuS; 1 ♂, same locality, 04.05.2008, E. Proskuryakov - YuS; 180 ♂♂, 96 ♀♀, same locality, 17.04.2009, 19-22.iv.2010, A. Shekhovtsov - ArS, YuS; 2 ♂♂, Kharkov reg., Zolochev. District, 1-2 km N Dolzhnik village, 01.v.2008, 11.v.2008 A. Shehovcov - ArS, YuS; 1 ♀, Kharkov reg., 1 km W Aeroport, 20.iv.2009, A. Shekhovtsov, B. Loboda - YuS; 112 ♂♂, 23 ♀♀, Kharkov reg., 1 km N Aeroport, 23-27.iv.2010, A. Shekhovtsov - ArS; 24 ♂, 9 ♀, Kharkov reg., Zolochev District, 4-5 km W Dolzhik village, 25.iv.2010, A. Shekhovtsov - ArS; 2 ♂♂, Kharkov reg., Izyum District, Malaya Kamyshevakhka, 27.iv.2010, A. Slutsky, B. Loboda - ArS.

Diagnosis. Body relatively big; antennae usually totally black, very rare 1st joint dark-red; prothorax lateral tubercles shortly angulated; pronotal longitudinal furrow not interrupted near middle by small convexity; pronotal longitudinal stripes in males very narrow and sometimes not complete; pronotum in males with moderately sparse big dots and fine dense punctation; male pronotum never with scattered black recumbent setae; males with mostly glabrous elytra; very rare males (several specimens from Kharkov city airport) with totally pubescent elytra, though male elytral pubescence is not very dense, specially along elytral carinae, which can be more or less shining; scattered recumbent setae in glabrous elytral area always absent; females are always autochromal with densely pubescent dark-brown elytra; dirty-white dorsal elytral stripes in females sometimes indistinct, but humeral stripes are always well developed; dorsal stripes can be interrupted by black dots; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) nearly indistinct; anterior part of humeral area with dense big dots disappearing before middle; fine elytral irregular striae never obliterated; elytra usually totally black up to the apices; legs usually dark-red or nearly black.

Body length in males: 9.8-13.6 mm, in females: 11.2-15.4 mm; body width in males: 3.8-5.0 mm, in females: 4.4-6.0 mm.

D. c. macropoides differs from the nominative subspecies by usually totally black legs, antennae and elytra, besides females are always with rather dark pubescence.

Marginal populations (Volchansk District) are of transitional character to the nominative subspecies with more reddish legs and 1st antennal joint.

Distribution. Kharkov Region in North-East Ukraine; known localities are: Izyum environs, 49°13'N 37°17'E - (Plavilstshikov, 1932a), ZMM; Izyum District, Malaya Kamyshevakhka, 49°06'N 37°13'E - ArS; Dokuchaevu, 49°54'N 36°26'E - MD, YuS, ArS; Kharkov environs - ZMM, AB; Kharkov city, centre - private communication by A. Shekhovtsov, 2010; Kharkov city, aeroport environs - ArS; Kharkov city, Pomerki - ZMM; Chervonyi Shakhter, Pridonetskoe Forestry, 49°11'N 37°03'E - AB; Novaya Vodolaga, 49°43'N 35°52'E - AB; Zolochev District, 1-2 km N Dolzhik village, 50°11'N 35°58'E - ArS.

Remark. The name of the taxon was introduced as *Dorcadion* (s. str.) *caucasicum* var. *macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932a and so available, but has never been used before as valid.

3. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium perroudi* Pic, 1942, new rank
(Figs 20-26, Photo 4)

Dorcadion sericatum var. *perroudi* Pic, 1942: 2 (“de Crimée”).

Dorcadion sericatum, Ganglbauer, 1884: 443 („Krim, Caucasus, Kleinasien“), part.

Dorcadion caucasicum, Plavilstshikov, 1948: 127, part.; 1965: 411, part.

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) caucasicum, Plavilstshikov, 1958: 118, part.; 1965: 411, part.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium, Breuning, 1958: 22 (“Crimée, Anatolie sept.”), part.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium morpho ♀ *perroudi*, Breuning, 1962: 364.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium cinerarium, Bartenev, 2004: 37, part; 2009: 300 part.

Type locality. Crimea - according to the original description, most probably Simferopol environs, where the taxon is most numerous.

Material examined. Ukraine, Crimea: 1 ♂, Feodosiya - ZIN; 54 ♂♂, 41 ♀♀, Alma River, Rybakov - ZIN; 6 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, Alushta, B.V.Stark - ZMM; 1 ♂, Simferopol, Dubki, 17.iv.1901, Kuznetsov - ZIN; 1 ♀, Yalta, 01.iv.1903, 22.vii.1973 - MD; 4 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀, Agarmysh, 29.iii.1906, Kirechenko - ZIN; 4 ♀♀, Agarmysh, 23-24.iv.1906 - ZIN; 2 ♂♂, Laspi, 19-25.v.1907, K.Yatsentkovskiy - ZIN; 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Belbek, 12-24.v.1907, Kuznetsov - ZIN; 6 ♀♀, Belbek, 14.v.1907, Kirechenko - ZIN; 1 ♂, Degermenki [now Zaprudnoe], 20.v.1907, Kirechenko - ZIN; 1 ♂, Babugan-Yayla, 18.vi.1911, V.Pligitskiy - ZIN; 1 ♀, Babugan-Yayla, 19.vi.1911, A.M.Dyakov - ZIN; 1 ♀, Sevastopol, Mekenzievyy Mt., 07.iv.1912, W.Pliginski - ZIN; 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Sevastopol, 15.iv.1904, 05.iii.1913, W.Pliginski - ZMM; 8 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀, Yalta, 12-13.iv.1903, 12.iv.1904, G.Suvorov - ZIN, ZMM; 1 ♂, Inkerman, 05.v.1903, Kuznetsov - ZIN; 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, Balaklava, 1908, Solomko - ZIN; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Baydary [now Orlioe], Yatsentkovskij, 25.iii.1907, 06.v.1907 - ZIN; 1 ♀, Alupka, 12.v.1912 - ZMM; 1 ♂, Kizil-Koba [now Krasnopescherno], 27.v.1912, W.Pliginski - ZIN; 1 ♀, Koreiz, 16.vii.1912 - ZMM; 5 ♂♂, Simeiz, 14-16.iv.1913, D.Romashov - ZMM; 1 ♂, Otuzskaya Valley, 12.iii.1916, V.Vuchetich - ZMM; 5 ♂♂, Gaspra, v.1926, V.A.Mindgolm - ZIN; 1 ♂, Natashino, 18.iv.1927 - ZMM; 1 ♂, Foros, vi.1930 - ZMM; 10 ♂♂, 20 ♀♀, Simferopol, 09.iv.1932 - ZMM; 3 ♂♂, Miskhor, 25.iv.1932, Rejkhard - ZIN; 1 ♀, Kuchuk-Koy [now Parkovoe], 11.v.1934 - ZMM; 1 ♀, Alushta, 22.iv.1935, Kryzhanovsky - ZIN; 2 ♀♀, Staryi Krym, 01.vi.1946 - ZIN; 1 ♀, Gurzuf, 13.iv.1948, K.Arnoldi - MD; 1 ♂, Alushta, 12.v.1955 - ZIN; 9 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, Karadag Mt., [44°54'N, 35°12'E], 23.iv.1955, 22.iv.1956 - ZMM; 4 ♂, 1 ♀, Staryi Krym, Kurskoe, 20.iv.1956 - ZMM; 1 ♂, Saki District, Mezhgornoe, 26.iv.1967, N.Maltseva - AB; 1 ♀, Simferopo 27.iv.1970, Berlov - MD; 1 ♂, Yaltinskaya-Yayla, 03.vi.1976, B.S.Pavlov - Verevkin - MPSU; 1 ♂, Belogorsk District, Novopsilovka [Novozhilovka], 15.v.1979, Postolatiy - AB; 1 ♀, Shchebetovka, 26.iv.1986, Bogolilova - MPSU; 1 ♂, Argamysh Mountain, 26.iv.1986, I. Korshunova - MPSU; 25 ♂♂, 18 ♀♀, Simferopol, Salgirka, 05-08.v.1987, K.Efetov - MD, ML; 5 ♂♂, Alushta, Verkhnyaya Kutuzovka, 07.vi.1987, 10.vi.1988, 08.iv.1989, K.Efetov - MD, ML; 2 ♂♂, Lozovoe, 09.iv.1988, K.Efetov - ML; 12 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, Simferopol, 24-29.iv.1988, 01.v.1991, 06.v.1991, K.Efetov - ML; 1 ♂, Simferopol, Marino, 30.iv.1988, K.Efetov - ML; 5 ♂♂, Sudak, 03.v.1988, 09.iv.1989, 14.iv.1991, K.Efetov - MD, ML; 1 ♂, Demerdzhi [now Luchistoe], 15.iv.1989, K.Efetov - MD; 2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, Belogorsk, Sary-Kaya, 14.iv.1990, K.Efetov - MD, ML; 1 ♀, Sudak, 21.iv.1991, K.Efetov - ML; 4 ♂♂, Alushta, Rabochiy Ugolok, 21.iv.1991, K.Efetov - ML; 3 ♂♂, Simferopol, Kamenka, 11.v.1991, K.Efetov - ML; 1 ♀, Simferopol, 18.iv.1992, K.Efetov - ML; 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Vladislavovka, 19.iv.1992, M.Danilevsky - MD; 1 ♂, Alushta, Chatyr-Dag, 7-10.v.1994, Yu.Tretyakov - AN; 1 ♂, Chatyr-Dag Ridge, Angarskiy Pass, 01.v.2004, Yu. Skrylnik - YuS; 3 ♂♂, Simferopol District, Dolgorukovskaya Yayla, Kizil-Koba Cave, 01-02.v.2004, Yu. Skrylnik - YuS; 3 ♂♂, Alushta District, N Demerdzhi Mountain, 01-03.v.2004, Yu. Skrylnik - YuS; 1 ♀, Alushta reg, Luchistoe vill., S. Demerdzhi Mountain, 44°44'55.14"N, 34°23'52.14"E, h=610 m, 21.vi.2010 leg. Yu. Skrylnik, A. Dronov, R. Bidychak - YuS.

Diagnosis. Body relatively big; antennae never totally black, 1st joint usually light-red, sometimes 3 or 4 basal antennal joints also red; prothorax lateral tubercles obtuse; pronotal longitudinal furrow not interrupted near middle by small convexity; pronotal longitudinal stripes in males very narrow and sometimes not complete; pronotum in males with moderately sparse big dots and fine dense punctation; male pronotum often with scattered black recumbent setae; males nearly always with mostly glabrous elytra; scattered recumbent setae

Photo 3. *D. c. macropoides*
 Plavilstshikov, 1932: Kharkov,
 Dokuchaev, Rogan, 49°52'41.70"N
 36°26'24.73"E, (photo by A.
 Shekhovtsov).

Figs 20-26. *D. c. perroudi* (Crimea):
 20- male, Kamenka; 21- male,
 Simferopol; 22- female, same
 locality; 23- female, same locality;
 24- female, Salgirka Park; 25- female,
 Sudak; 26- female, Belogorsk, Sary-
 Kaya.

Photo 4. *D. c. perroudi* Pic, 1942: Crimea, Tyurke yayla, 1100 -1200 m, 44°48'N, 34°25', 03.05.2010 (photo by A. Shekhovtsov).

Figs 27-30. *D. c. zubovi* ssp. nov. (Moldova): 27- Holotype, male, Rezeny (present designation); 28-30- Paratype, female, same locality (present designation).

Photo 5. *D. c. zubovi* ssp. nov.: Moldova, Rezeny, 46°45'N, 28°54', 26.03.2010, (photo by A. Zubov).

in glabrous elytral often present; very rare males (several specimens from near Simferopol) with totally pubescent elytra, male elytral pubescence can be very dense; females are usually autochromal with densely pubescent elytra; elytral pubescence in females usually more or less pale with contrast dirty-white humeral and dorsal elytral stripes; dorsal stripes can be sometimes diffused and nearly indistinct, often with numerous black spots; sometimes female pubescence dark-brown with more or less contrast pale stripes; very rare female elytral pubescence is totally black without humeral and dorsal pale stripes; only one androchromal female with glabrous shining elytra known (Belogorsk environs); longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) nearly indistinct; anterior part of humeral area with dense big dots disappearing before middle; fine elytral irregular striae more or less obliterated; apical elytral margin usually reddish; legs usually light-red.

Body length in males: 9.8-13.2 mm, in females: 11.3-15.5 mm; body width in males: 3.8-4.9 mm, in females: 4.8-6.4 mm.

D. c. perroudi is the lightest known subspecies, usually with bright-red 1st antennal joint and legs; besides it differs from other subspecies of the group by numerous pubescent forms of females, which can be rather pale or very dark, with or without distinct elytral pale stripes.

It differs from the geographically closest subspecies (*D.c. panticapaeum*, *D. c. bartenevi*), which are distributed along its west, east and north borders by usually glabrous elytra in males.

Distribution. Ukraine, south half of Crimean Peninsula, southwards 45°30'N.

A lot of localities known: Agarmysh Mountain, 45°02'N, 35°02'E - ZIN, MPSU; Alma River [between Sevastopol and Eupatoria] - ZIN; Alupka, 44°25'N, 34°02'E - ZMM; Alushta, 44°40'N, 34°24'E - ZIN, ZMM; Angarskiy Pass, 44°45'N, 34°20'E - YuS; Babugan-Yayla - ZIN; Balaklava, 44°30'N, 33°36'E - ZIN; Belbek River [between Sevastopol and Bakhchisaray] - ZIN; Chatyr-Dag, 44°46'N, 34°17'E - AN; Dolgorukovskaya yayla, 44°49'-50'N, 34°23'E - private message by Shekhovtsov, 2011; Dubki, 44°56'N, 34°01'E - ZIN; Feodosiya, 45°02'N, 35°22'E - ZIN; Foros, 44°23'N, 33°47'E - ZMM; Gaspra, 44°25'N, 34°06'E - ZIN; Gurzuf, 44°33'N, 34°17'E - MD; Inkerman, 44°36'N, 33°36'E - ZIN; Kamenka, 44°59'N, 34°10'E - ML; Karadag Mountain, 44°55'N, 35°13'E - ZMM; Koreiz, 44°25'N, 34°05'E - ZMM; Krasnopeshchernaya, 44°51'N, 34°20'E - ZIN, YuS; Kurskoe, 45°01'N, 34°56'E - ZMM; Laspi, 44°25'N, 33°43'E - ZIN; Lozovoe, 44°54'N, 34°09'E - ML; Luchistoe, 44°44'N, 34°24'E - MD, Bartenev, 2009; Marino, 44°55'N, 34°08'E - ML; Mekenzievy Mountain - ZIN; Miskhor, 44°25'N, 34°05'E - ZIN; Mezhgornoe, 45°06'N, 33°51'E - AB; Natashino, 45°24'N, 33°16'E - ZMM; North Demerdzhi Mountain, 44°46'N, 34°23'E - YuS; Novopsilovka [Novozhilovka?, 45°09'N, 34°14'E] - AB; Orlineo, 44°26'N, 33°46'E - ZIN; Otuzskaya Valley - ZMM; Parkovoe, 44°24'N, 33°54'E - ZMM; Perevalnoe, 44°51'N, 34°19' - private message by Shekhovtsov, 2011; Privalnoe - Bartenev, 2009; Rabochiy Ugolok, Western Alushta - ML; Sary-Kaya Rock - MD, ML; Sevastopol, 44°36'N, 33°32'E - ZIN, ZMM, MPSU; Shchebetovka, 44°56'N, 35°09'E - MPSU; Simeiz, 44°24'N, 33°59'E - ZMM; Simferopol, 44°56'N, 34°06'E - ZIN, ZMM, MD, ML; Simferopol, 44°59'N, 34°07'E - private message by Shekhovtsov, 2011; Simferopol, Borodina street, 44°58'N, 34°08'E - private message by Shekhovtsov, 2011; Simferopol, Salgirka Park,

44°56'38.11"N, 34°07'44.18"E - MD, ML; Staryi Krym, 45°01'N, 35°05'E - ZIN; South Demerdzhi Mountain, 44°44'N, 34°23'E - YuS; Sudak, 44°51'N, 34°58'E - MD, ML; Tyurke yayla, 1100 -1200 m, 44°48'N, 34°25' - private message by Shekhovtsov, 2011; Verkhnyaya Kutuzovka, 44°43'N, 34°22'E - MD, ML; Vladislavovka, 45°09'N, 35°22'E - MD; Yalta, 44°29'N, 34°09'E - ZIN, MD; Yaltinskaya-Yayla, 44°33'N, 34°08'E - MPSU; Zaprudnoe, 44°35'N, 34°19'E - ZIN.

Remark. The name of the taxon was introduced as *Dorcadion sericatum* var. *perroudi* Pic, 1942 and so available, but has never been used before as valid.

4. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium zubovi* ssp. nov.

(Figs 27-30, Photo 5)

Dorcadion sericatum, Miller & Zubowsky, 1906: 63 („Kischineff“, „Bendery“); 1910: 138 („Kishinev“, „Bendery“); 1917: 138 („Kishinev“, „Bendery“).

Dorcadion (s. str.) *caucasicum*, Plavilstshikov, 1931: 74 („aus Bessarabien, u. zw. aus Kishinev“).

Dorcadion caucasicum, Medvedev & Shapiro, 1957: 198 („Kishinev“, „Bendery“).

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium, Chyubchik, 2010: 116 („Yaloveny distr., Raezeni vill. env.“).

Type locality. Moldova, 500 m SW Rezeny, 69 m, 46°45'22,17"N, 28°53'49,55"E

Type material. Holotype (♂): Moldova, Rezeny environs, 19.iv.2009, A.Zubov - ML. Paratype: (1 ♂): Orkhey (before Orgeev) District, Korneshty, 1902, Zubov - ZIN; (54 ♂♂, 16 ♀♀): Rezeny environs, 26.iv.2006, 09.v.2006, A.Zubov - AS, ML; (1 ♀): Rezeny, 29.iii.2008, 46°45'N 28°53'E, A. Zubov - ML; (16 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀): Yaloveny District, Rezeny, 14.v.2008, 19.iv.2009. A.Zubov - AZ, MD; (115 ♂♂, 59 ♀♀): Rezeny, 19.iv.2009, 26.iii.2010, 46°45'N, 28°54', A.Zubov - AZ, MD; (19 ♂♂, 1 ♀): Leova District, between Kyzlyar, 46°38'N, 28°31'E and Knyazevka, 46°37'N, 28°28'E, 01.v.2010 - AZ, MD.

Diagnosis. Body moderately big; antennae black with red 1st joint; prothorax lateral tubercles shortly angulated and a little attenuated; pronotal longitudinal furrow usually interrupted near middle by small convexity; pronotal longitudinal stripes in males very narrow and sometimes not complete; pronotum in males with moderately dense big dots and fine dense punctation; male pronotum usually with scattered black recumbent setae; males are always with mostly glabrous elytra; scattered recumbent setae in glabrous elytral area always absent; females are usually androchromal with glabrous shining elytra; sometimes (especially from the Rezeny) autochromal females are represented by considerable number of specimen, but elytral female pubescence is never dense and always dark-brown; females with pale elytral pubescence unknown; pale dorsal elytral stripes in autochromal females often indistinct, but humeral stripes usually more or less pronounced; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) nearly indistinct; anterior part of humeral area with dense big dots disappearing before middle; fine elytral irregular striae more or less obliterated; apical elytral margin usually reddish; legs red.

Body length in males: 9.7-12.7 mm, in females: 9.8-12.8 mm; body width in males: 3.5-4.2 mm, in females: 4.3-5.2 mm.

D. c. zubovi ssp. nov. differs from all other subspecies by the domination of glabrous females in all populations; besides it differs from the neighbouring nominative subspecies by lighter legs and 1st antennal joint.

Distribution. Most part of Moldova territory with only exception of southern regions, where *D. c. gorodinskii* is distributed; known localities are: Kishinev - (Miller & Zubowsky, 1906, 1910, 1917; Plavilstshikov, 1931; Medvedev & Shapiro, 1957); Bendery, 46°49'N, 29°28'E - (Miller & Zubowsky, 1910, 1917; Medvedev & Shapiro, 1957); Korneshty, 47°21'N, 28°00'E - ZIN; 500 m SW Rezeny, 69m, 46°45'22"-17"N, 28°53'49"-55"E and 1 km S Rezeny, 85m, 46°45'06"-44'58"N, 28°54'24"-35"E - AS, AZ, MD, ML; Leova District, between Kyzlyar, 46°38'N, 28°31'E and Knyazevka, 46°37'N, 28°28'E - AZ, MD.

Etymology. The new subspecies is dedicated to Andrey Zubov (Kishinev), who collected most type specimens.

Remark. The corresponding populations were not known to Plavilstshikov (1958); according to him the western border of the species (as *D. caucasicum*) is Dnepr River.

5. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium veniamini* ssp. nov.

(Figs 31-32, Photo 6)

Type locality. Krasnodar Region, Novorossiysk environs, Markotkh Ridge, Andreevsky Pass, from 44°43'30.56"N, 37°52.03'72"E to 44°43'29.10"N, 37°52'24.59"E.

Type material. Holotype (♂): Krasnodar reg., Novorossiysk environs, Andreevsky Pass, 500 m, 44°43'N, 37°52'E, 03.vi.2010, M. Danilevsky leg. - MD; Paratypes: (109 ♂♂, 46 ♀♀): same locality, 02-05.vi.2010, V. & A. Babenko, O. Gambaryan, E. Gonsales, T., D. & V. Gusev, M. Danilevsky, N. Danilevskaya, G. & V. Guskov, A. & M. Lazarenko and R. Ruban leg. - MD, ML; (1 ♂): Novorossiysk, P.N.Novitsky - ZIN; (2 ♂♂, 1 ♀): same locality, 30.v.1928, 01.vi.1928, Baeckmann - ZIN; (1 ♂): same locality, 22.iv.1906 - ZIN; (1 ♂): same locality, 1909, N.N.Bogdanov-Katkov - ZIN; (17 ♂♂, 17 ♀♀): same locality, 23-25.v.2008, A.Abramov - MD; 1 ♂, Gelendzhik, Markotkh Ridge, 21.v.1990, P.Rybnov - MPSU; (1 ♂): same locality, 11.v.1995, V.Gnezdilov - ZIN; (2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀): NW Novorossiyska, Markotkh Ridge, 600 m, 23-27.v.2005, A.Abramov - MD.

Diagnosis. Body big - the biggest known subspecies; antennae black with red 1st joint; prothorax lateral tubercles attenuated and a little sharpened; pronotal longitudinal furrow rather shallow, sometimes indistinct; pronotal longitudinal stripes in males very narrow or absent; pronotum in males with dense and rough, partly conjugated big dots; fine punctuation often indistinct near middle; male pronotum sometimes with scattered black recumbent setae; males are always with mostly glabrous elytra; scattered recumbent setae in glabrous elytral area always absent; females are always autochromal with elytra covered by very fine dark-brown pubescence; pale dorsal elytral stripes usually indistinct, humeral stripes distinct, but very narrow; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) distinct anteriorly; anterior part of humeral area with dense big dots and rough punctuation is often protruding behind middle; fine elytral irregular striae obliterated; apical elytral margin usually reddish; legs red.

Body length in males: 11.5-15.5 mm, in females: 13.1-16.1 mm; body width in males: 4.0-5.6 mm, in females: 5.0-6.4 mm.

D. c. veniamini ssp. nov. differs from all other subspecies by well developed prothoracic lateral tubercles, by relatively rough pronotal and elytral sculpture and by very special form of females with totally pubescent dark elytra without dorsal stripes. It differs from the geographically closest *D. c. adygorum* ssp. nov. (a single male known) by rough pronotal sculpture, strong thoracic tubercles and big size.

Distribution. South-west Russia, Krasnodar Region, Markotkh Ridge from about Novorossiysk environs (Andreevsky Pass, 44°43'N 37°52'E) to about Gelendzhik environs - ZIN, MPSU, MD, ML.

Etymology. The new subspecies is dedicated to Veniamin Babenko, who collected a considerable number of type specimens.

6. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium adygorum* ssp. nov.

(Fig. 33)

Type locality. South Russia, Adygeya Republic, Maykop environs.

Type material. Holotype (♂): with two labels: 1) [North Caucasus, Maykop, 20.v.1932][in Russian]; 2) *Dorcadion caucasicum* Küst, V. Selivanovskij det. - ZMM.

Diagnosis. A single male known; body relatively small; antennae black with dark-red 1st joint; prothorax lateral tubercles very short, obtuse; pronotal longitudinal furrow shallow and interrupted near middle by small convexity; pronotal longitudinal stripe narrow, but complete; pronotum relatively smooth with sparse small dots and very fine microsculpture; pronotum covered with distinct short recumbent black setae; elytra mostly glabrous; several scattered recumbent setae in glabrous elytral area present; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) indistinct; anterior part of humeral area with a few big dots; fine elytral irregular striae very distinct; apical elytral margin reddish; legs dark-red.

Body length: 11.0 mm, body width: 4.3 mm.

D. c. adygorum ssp. nov. is not close to its geographical neighbour *D. c. veniamini* ssp. nov. because of rather fine pronotal sculpture, obtuse thoracic tubercles and small size; it looks to be close to the nominative subspecies, because of just same prothorax morphology, but pronotal black recumbent pubescence is not so distinct in any other subspecies of *D. cinerarium*, besides well developed irregular elytral striae are usually absent in *D. c. cinerarium*. All morphological characters of the holotype could be just individual peculiarities, but the subspecies status of Maykop population is quite evident because of its strong geographical isolation from all other populations of the species.

Distribution. South Russia, Adygeya Republic, Maykop environs - ZMM.

Etymology. The name of the new subspecies is created based on the name of Caucasian people of the region - Adygs.

7. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium terkense* ssp. nov.

(Fig. 34)

Type locality. Chechnya: Groznyi environs.

Type material. Holotype (♂): Caucas bor., Groznyi, v.1913, N.Plavilstshikov - ZMM. Paratypes (2 ♂♂): with same label - ZMM.

Photo 6. *D. c. veniamini* ssp. nov.: Krasnodar reg., Novorossiysk environs, Andreevsky Pass, 500 m, 44°43'N, 37°52'E, (photo by M. Danilevsky).

Figs 31-32. *D. c. veniamini* ssp. nov. (Krasnodar Region): 31- Holotype, male, Novorossiysk environs, Andreevsky Pass, (present designation). 32- Paratype, female, Novorossiysk environs (present designation).

Fig. 33. *D. c. adygorum* ssp. nov.: 33- Holotype, male, Adygeya Republic, Maykop (present designation).

Fig. 34. *D. c. terkense* ssp. nov.: 34- Holotype, male, Groznyi (present designation).

Fig. 35. *D. c. deniz* ssp. nov.: 35- Holotype, male, Azerbaijan, Baku (present designation).

Fig. 36-37. *D. c. napolovi* ssp. nov.: 36- Holotype, male, Azerbaijan, Shemakha, Pirkuniskiy Natural Reserve (present designation). 37- Paratype, female, same locality (present designation).

Fig. 38. *D. c. belousovi* ssp. nov.: 38- Holotype, male, Azerbaijan, Kuba, Velvelichay River, (present designation).

Fig. 39. *D. c. smetanai* ssp. nov.: 39- Holotype, male, Khasaut (present designation).

Fig. 40. *D. c. azovense* ssp. nov.: 40- Holotype, male, Berdyansk (present designation).

Figs 41-43. *D. c. skrylniki* ssp. nov.: 41- Holotype, male, 2 km E Novoe, 5 km SW Melitopol, (present designation).
42-43- Paratype, female, same locality (present designation).

Photo 7. *D. c. skrylniki* ssp. nov.: Melitopol env., (photo by Yu. Skrylnik).

Diagnosis. Only 3 males known; body moderately big antennae black with red 1st joint; prothorax lateral tubercles attenuated and a little sharpened; pronotal longitudinal furrow rather shallow; pronotal longitudinal stripe indistinct (probably lost); pronotum with dense, irregular big dots; fine punctation partly indistinct near middle; male pronotum with scattered black recumbent setae; elytra in two specimens with poor traces of black pubescence along shallow furrows, but in holotype - mostly glabrous; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) distinct anteriorly; anterior part of humeral area with dense big conjugated dots, and rough punctation is protruding behind middle; fine elytral irregular striae obliterated; apical elytral margin usually reddish; legs red.

Body length in males: 10.6-12.4 mm; body width in males: 3.8-4.4 mm.

New subspecies is close to *D. c. veniamini* ssp. nov. because of similar rough pronotal and elytral sculpture and well developed prothoracic tubercles, but differs by the presence of elytral pubescence in certain specimens. This character is typical for all subspecies of the next group distributed along sea coasts and was never observed the subspecies of the nominative group.

Distribution. Central part of North Caucasus Chechnya, Groznyi environs - ZMM.

Etymology. The name of the new subspecies is created based on the name of Terek River in certain several Caucasian languages - Terk.

8. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium deniz* ssp. nov.

(Fig. 35)

Type locality. East Azerbaijan, Baku environs.

Type material. Holotype (♂): "Env. de Baku, iv.1959, leg. Bogačev. - MD.

Diagnosis. A single male known; body relatively small; antennae black with dark-red 1st joint; prothorax lateral tubercles relatively long, attenuated and a little sharpened; pronotal longitudinal furrow shallow and interrupted near middle by small convexity; pronotal longitudinal stripe narrow; pronotum very smooth and shining with sparse small dots and very fine microsculpture; pronotum without black setae; elytra mostly glabrous, strongly shining, without black setae; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) indistinct; anterior part of humeral area with a few conjugated big dots; anterior part of humeral carinae roughly sculptured; fine elytral irregular striae very indistinct; apical elytral margin reddish; legs bright-red.

Body length: 11.3 mm, body width: 3.9 mm.

The taxon differs from all other subspecies by strongly shining cuticle and very sparse pronotal punctation.

Distribution. Azerbaijan, Baku environs - MD.

Etymology. The name „deniz“ is a noun in apposition, which means “see“ in Turkish.

9. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium napolovi* ssp. nov.

(Figs 36-37)

Type locality. Azerbaijan, Shemakha environs, Pirkuli Natural Reserve.

Type material. Holotype (♂): Azerbaijan - NE, Shemakha [= Şamaxı] distr., Pirkuliskiy Nat. Res., 3.vi.1984, lg. D. Logunov - ML; Paratypes: (2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀): same locality, 18.v.1984, 25.v.1984, lg. D. Logunov - AN, ML, MD; (1 ♂): Shemakha distr., Demerchi, 08.vii.1937, A.Bogachev - MD; (1 ♂): Shemakha, 22.vii.1937, A.Bogachev - ML.

Diagnosis. Body of middle size; antennae black with red 1st joint; prothorax lateral tubercles relatively short, slightly angulated; pronotal longitudinal furrow shallow and interrupted near middle by small convexity; pronotal longitudinal stripe indistinct; pronotum with strong and

dense punctation; pronotal microsculpture distinct; very short recumbent black setae present; elytra mostly glabrous, shining, but very short scattered setae sometimes visible all over elytral surface; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) indistinct; anterior part of humeral area without conjugated big dots; anterior part of humeral carinae without rough sculpture; fine elytral irregular striae distinct; apical elytral margin reddish; legs red.

Body length in males: 11.7-13.2 mm, in females: 12.7-13.5 mm; body width in males: 4.2-4.6 mm, in females: 5.4- 5.7 mm.

The taxon differs from the nearest *D. c. belousovi* ssp. nov. by the absence of wide pronotal smooth line; 1st antennal joint red, posterior elytral margin red, legs much lighter.

Distribution. Azerbaijan, Shemakha environs, Pirkuli Natural Reserve, about 40°46'N, 48°32'E - ML, AN; Shemakha environs, 40°38'N, 48°38'E - ML; Demerchi, 40°50'N, 48°33'E - MD.

Etymology. The taxon is dedicated to Alexander Napolov (Riga, Latvia), who collected most type specimens.

10. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium belousovi* ssp. nov. (Fig. 38)

Type locality. Azerbaijan, Kuba District, Velvelichay River, 1800 m.

Type material. Holotype (♂): "Azerbaydzhan, Kuba District, Velvelichay River, 1800 m, 25.iv.1982, I. Belousov leg." - MD.

Diagnosis. A single male known; body relatively big; antennae totally black; prothorax lateral tubercles very short, obliterated; pronotal longitudinal furrow absent, but wide smooth line distinct; pronotal longitudinal stripe indistinct (lost because of poor condition of the specimen?); pronotum very shining with very dense and rough punctation along smooth line, microsculpture distinct; pronotum without black setae; elytra glabrous, with distinct microsculpture, without black setae; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) indistinct; anterior part of humeral area without big dots; anterior elytral area without big dots; fine elytral irregular striae hardly visible; apical elytral margin totally black; legs dark-red.

Body length: 13.5 mm, width: 4.9 mm.

The taxon differs from all other subspecies by special pronotal sculpture with wide longitudinal smooth line and rough lateral punctation.

Distribution. North-East Azerbaijan, Kuba District, Velvelichay River, 1800 m, about 41°13'N, 48°38'E - MD.

Etymology. The taxon is dedicated to a well-known specialist in Carabidae Igor Alexandrovich Belousov, who collected the holotype.

II. "*Dorcadion cinerarium panticapaeum*-group"

All males always with totally pubescent elytra; females also with totally pubescent elytra and usually with distinct pale dorsal stripes.

7 subspecies are accepted here.

11. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium smetanai* ssp. nov.

(Fig. 39)

Type locality. South Russia, Karachay-Cherkessia Republic, Khasaut environs.

Type material. Holotype (♂): Caucasus, Kosout, 3.v.09][in Russian] / ZMM. Paratype (1 ♂): [North Caucasus, Baksan, 19.v.1955, Azarov][in Russian] - ZIN.

Diagnosis. A single male known; body relatively small; antennae black with dark-red 1st joint; prothorax lateral tubercles very short, obtuse; pronotal longitudinal furrow shallow and interrupted near middle by small convexity; pronotal longitudinal stripe narrow; pronotum relatively smooth with sparse small dots and very fine distinct microsculpture; pronotum and elytra covered with dense black pubescence; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) moderately developed; anterior part of humeral area with a few small dots; fine elytral irregular striae indistinct; elytra totally black up to the apices; legs dark-red.

Body length: 9.6-13.9 mm, body width: 3.5-5.0 mm.

D. c. smetanai ssp. nov. differs from all closely related subspecies of North Caucasus by totally pubescent elytra.

Distribution. South Russia: Karachay-Cherkessia Republic, Khasaut environs, 43°42'N, 42°30'E (ZMM) and Kabardino-Balkar Republic, Baksan environs, 43°41'N, 43°31'E (ZIN).

Etymology. The taxon is dedicated to a great Czech entomologist Aleš Smetana.

12. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium azovense* ssp. nov.

(Fig. 40)

Type locality. Ukraine: Berdyansk environs.

Type material. Holotype (♂): "Berdyansk, 06.iv.1932" - MD. Paratype (1 ♂): with same label - ML.

Diagnosis. Only 2 males available; body relatively small; antennae black with dark-red 1st joint; prothorax lateral tubercles obtuse; pronotal longitudinal furrow very shallow, but not interrupted near middle; pronotal longitudinal stripes very narrow, but distinct; pronotum with moderately sparse big dots and fine dense punctation, without black pubescence; elytra densely covered with black pubescence; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) a little pronounced anteriorly; anterior part of humeral area with several big dots disappearing before middle; fine elytral irregular striae indistinct; apical elytral margin usually reddish; legs dark-red.

Body length: 9.5-11.2 mm; body width: 3.8-4.2 mm.

D. c. azovense ssp. nov. is the easternmost representative of the group in the northern bank of Azov Sea. It considerably differs from geographically closest *D. c. sckrylniki* ssp. nov. by much bigger size and elongated body, besides pronotum in males of *D. c. sckrylniki* ssp. nov. with a little bigger punctation and can never be pubescent. *D. c. azovense* ssp. nov. is very similar to *D. c. panticapaeum*, which has much more distinct elytral furrows.

Distribution. Berdyansk environs, South-East Ukraine - MD, ML.

Etymology. The name of the new subspecies is created based on the name of Azov Sea.

13. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium skrylniki* ssp. nov.

(Figs 41-43, Photo 7)

Type locality. Ukraine: 5 km SW Melitopol, 2 km E Novoe, 46°47'N, 35°18'E.

Type material. Holotype (♂): Ukraine, 2 km E Novoe, 5 km SW Melitopol, 46°47'N 35°18'E, 24.iv.2009, Yu. Skrylnik - MD. Paratypes: (106 ♂♂, 61 ♀♀): same locality, 24.iv.2009, 30.iv.2010, 5.v.2011, Yu. Skrylnik leg. - YuS, MD, ML; (1 ♀): same locality, 24.iv.2009, B. Podoprigora leg. - YuS; (1 ♂): same locality, 30.iv.2010, R. Bidychak & A. Dronov leg. - YuS; (1 ♂): Ukraine, Melitopol environs, Molochnyi Liman, 25.iv.2004, A.Perevozov - MPSU.

Diagnosis. Body small and wide – the smallest known subspecies; antennae black with red 1st joint, which can be sometimes light-red or nearly black; prothorax lateral tubercles obtuse, shortly angulated, sometimes a little attenuated or just contrary obliterated; pronotal longitudinal furrow in males usually indistinct or hardly visible; pronotal longitudinal stripes very narrow, often indistinct; pronotal sculpture in males rather variable, usually with moderately sparse big dots and fine dense punctation, or rather smooth with several scattered small dots; males pronotal black pubescence distinct in fresh specimens; male elytra densely covered with black pubescence; females always autochromal with densely pubescent pale elytra; dorsal pale stripes usually diffused or sometimes rather contrast, with or without black spots; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) usually more or less developed, but sometimes totally obliterated; anterior part of humeral area with several big dots disappearing before middle; fine elytral irregular striae indistinct; apical elytral margin usually reddish; legs red or dark-red.

Body length in males: 8.7-12.0 mm, in females: 9.3-13.5 mm; body width in males: 3.1-4.1 mm, in females: 4.2-5.4 mm.

D. c. skrylniki ssp. nov. differs from neighbouring subspecies *D. c. azovense* ssp. nov. and *D. c. panticapaeum* first of all by very small body, which is relatively wide, especially in females.

Distribution. Black Sea coast of SW Ukraine in Melitopol environs, two localities known: 2 km E Novoe, 5 km SW Melitopol, 46°47'N, 35°18'E - YuS, MD, ML and Molochnyi Liman, about 46°41'N, 35°19'E - MPSU.

Etymology. The new subspecies is dedicated to Yuriy Skrylnik (Kharkov), who collected most type specimens.

14. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium panticapaeum* Plavilstshikov, 1951

(Figs 44-53)

Dorcadion (s.str.) *panticapaeum* Plavilstshikov, 1951: 116 (“Krym: okr. Kerchi”).

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium morpha ♂ *densevestitum* Breuning, 1946: 117 („Kertsch, Crimée“); 1962: 365.

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) panticapaeum, Plavilstshikov, 1958: 138; Lobanov et al., 1982: 263, part

Dorcadion panticapaeum, Zahaikevitch, 1991: 148; Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997: 64; Miroshnikov, 2004: 136.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) panticapaeum, Breuning, 1962: 366; Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 33; Bartenev, 2004: 37; 2009: 302.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium morpha ♂ *sericeovestitum* Breuning, 1962: 365 („Krim: Kertsch“).
Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium morpha ♀ *disconigromaculatum* Breuning, 1946: 118 („Kertsch, Crimée“); 1962: 366.
Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium morpha ♀ *densealbovestitum* Breuning, 1946: 118 („Kertsch, Crimée“); 1962: 366.
Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium gorodinskii Danilevsky, 1996: 65, part.
Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium panticipaeum, Danilevsky, 2010a: 245.

Type locality. Ukraine, Kerch Peninsula, Kerch environs - according to the original description.

Type material. Lectotype, ♂, (designated by Danilevsky, 2008) with 3 labels: 1) "Kertsch, Krim, 5.IV.07, Kiritschenko", 2) "*Dorcadion panticipaeum* m. Plavilstshikov det.", 3) "LECTOTYPUS *Dorcadion* (s.str) *PANTICIPAEUM* Plavilstshikov, 1951 M.Danilevsky des, 2008"; 7 Paralectotypes (designated by Danilevsky, 2008): 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, 1) "Kertsch, Krim, 5.IV.07, Kiritschenko", 2) "*Dorcadion panticipaeum* m. Plavilstshikov det.", 3) "PARALECTOTYPUS *Dorcadion* (s.str) *PANTICIPAEUM* Plavilstshikov, 1951 M.Danilevsky des, 2008"; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, 1) "Kerch, Krim, 8.4.08, W.Pliginski"; 2) "*Dorcadion panticipaeum* m. Plavilstshikov det.", 3) "PARALECTOTYPUS *Dorcadion* (s.str) *PANTICIPAEUM* Plavilstshikov, 1951 M.Danilevsky des, 2008"; 1 ♂, 1) "Kertsch, IV.15 (Krim)"; 2) "*Dorcadion panticipaeum* m. Plavilstshikov det.", 3) "PARALECTOTYPUS *Dorcadion* (s.str) *PANTICIPAEUM* Plavilstshikov, 1951 M.Danilevsky des, 2008";

Other material studied. 6 ♂♂, 8 ♀♀, Kerch - ZIN; 4 ♀♀, same locality, W.Pliginski - ZIN; 3 ♀♀, same locality, Kiretchenko - ZIN; 5 ♂♂, 12 ♀♀, same locality, 10.iv.1896, 08.iv.1901, 02-03.iv.1906, 08-11.iv.1906, 16.iv.1906, W. Pliginski - ZIN, ZMM, MD; 3 ♂, 6 ♀♀, same locality, 01-26.iv, P.Zhikharev - ZMM; 2 ♀♀, same locality, 1902, Kiretchenko - ZIN; 7 ♂♂, 27 ♀♀, same locality, 18.ii.1901, 13.iii.1901, 05.iii.1902, 10.iv.1902, 15.iii.1903, 20.iii.1903, 24.iv.1903, 13-14.iii.1906, 16.iii.1906, 30.iii.1906, 04.iv.1906, 10.iv.1906, 05.iv.1906, 07.iv.1915 - ZIN; 5 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, same locality, 25.iv.1901, N.Kuznetsov - ZIN; 14 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀, same locality, 25.iv.1903, 13-14.iii.1906, 08-10.iv.1906, 29.iv.1906, 05.iv.1907, 22.iv.1907, 20.iv.1918, Kiretchenko - ZIN, ZMM; 4 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, same locality, 24.iv.1907, Ilin - ZIN; 2 ♀♀, same locality, iv.1908, A.Leb - MD; 4 ♂♂, Kerch, Yuzaba, 24.iv.1901, 24.x.1907, N.Kuznetsov - ZIN; 1 ♀, Kazantip, 02.v.1923, Arnoldi - MD; 1 ♂, Krym, Oktyabr, Pyatikhatka River, 13.iv.1954, I.Maltsev - AB; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Sovkhoz Primorye [about 45°07'N, 35°30'E], 18.05.1956, Topchiev - MD; 1 ♂, Krym, Dzhankoy, 12.v.1976, N.Postolatiy - AB; 1 ♂, Krym, Uyutnoe, 14.v.1967, V.Grishkov - AB; 3 ♂♂, Krasnodar reg., Taman, 19.v.1981, A.Bartenev - AB; 1 ♂, same locality, 19.v.1981, A.Lobanov - MD; 1 ♂, Kherson, Turetsky Val, iv.1982 - MD; 2 ♂♂, Kerch, Mitridat Mountain, 07.iv.1983, Mosyakin - AB; 1 ♂, Krasnodar reg., Taman, Karabetova Mt., Taman Station, 14.iv.1986, Zamotaylov - MD; 21 ♂♂, 18 ♀♀, Kazantip, 02.v.1987, 09.v.1987, 16.v.1987, 31.v.1987, 21.iv.1990, 03.v.1992, Efetov - MD, ML; 1 ♂, Kerch, 03.vi.1987, Efetov - MPSU; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, 10 m, Kazantip, 21-25.iv.1992, M.Danilevsky - MD; 29 ♂♂, 12 ♀♀, Krasnodar reg., Taman, Karabetova Mt., 4-5km eastwards Taman Station, 24.iv.1992, v.1996, 18-20.v.2005, A.Abramov - MD; 4 ♂♂, 10 km W Fontan 75 m, 26.iv.1992, M.Danilevsky - MD; 8 ♂♂, 1 ♀, 120 m, Bagerovo, 28.iv.1992, M.Danilevsky - MD; 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, Krasnodar reg., Taman, 14.iv.1995, A.Abramov - AN; 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, S Ukraine, Chongar, 25.iv-01.v.1996, R.Mishustin - MD; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, [20-25 km E] Shchelkino, v.1999 - AB; 8 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀, Lenino District, Mysovoe, 45°26'55.41"N, 35°50'27.66"E, 04.v.2010, Yu. Skrylnik - YuS; 4 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀, Kazantip, 45°27'32.78"N, 35°51'23.18"E, 05.v.2010, Yu. Skrylnik, A. Dronov, R. Bidychak - YuS.

Diagnosis. Body small; antennae black with dark-red 1st joint, which can be sometimes nearly black or rather light; prothorax lateral tubercles obtuse, shortly angulated, nearly obliterated; pronotal longitudinal furrow in males usually shallow or very distinct; pronotal longitudinal stripes usually wide and distinct, sometimes narrow; pronotum usually with moderately sparse big dots and fine dense punctation; males pronotal black pubescence distinct; male elytra densely covered with black pubescence, the clear rudiments of pale humeral stripes often present; females always autochromal with densely pubescent pale elytra; dorsal pale stripes usually diffused or sometimes rather contrast, with or without black spots; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) usually more or less developed, but sometimes totally obliterated; anterior part of humeral area with several big dots disappearing before middle;

fine elytral irregular striae usually distinct; apical elytral margin usually reddish; legs red or dark-red.

Body length in males: 9.0-13.0 mm, in females: 9.7-13.0 mm; body width in males: 3.2-4.3 mm, in females: 4.1-5.9 mm.

D. c. panticapaeum differs from the closest subspecies *D. c. bartenevi* ssp. nov. by very dense elytral pubescence; besides pronotal punctation is rather small with poor microsculpture, poorly developed and lateral thoracic tubercles.

Distribution. Perekop Isthmus, Chongar Peninsula, east part of Crimean Peninsula including Kerch Peninsula (Ukraine) and Taman Peninsula (Krasnodar Region, Russia); several localities are known: Chongar Peninsula (Kherson Region) - MD; Turetsky Val (Perekop Isthmus), about 46°08'N, 33°41'E - MD; Oktyabr, Pyatikhatka River [45°19'N, 34°16'E] - AB; Uytutnoe, 45°31'N, 34°35'E - AB; Dzhanikoy, 45°42'N, 34°23'E - AB; Kerch environs, 45°20'N, 36°28'E - ZIN, ZMM, MPSU, MD, Bartenev, 2009; Kazantip Cape - YuS, MD; Shchelkino [20-25 km eastwards Kazantip Cape] - AB, Bartenev, 2009; Mysovoe, 45°26'55.41"N, 35°50'27.66"E - YuS; 10 km westwards Fontan, about 45°15'N, 35°53'E - MD; Bagerovo, 45°22'N, 36°17'E - MD; Mitridat Mountain, 45°20'54"N, 36°28'02"E - AB; Taman environs, 45°13'N, 36°43'E - AB, AN; Taman Peninsula, Karabetova Mountain [45°12'02"N, 36°46'51"E], 4-5 km eastwards Taman - MD; Yuzaba - ZIN.

Remarks. Three males with pubescent elytra from north-east Crimea (Pyatikhatka River, Uytutnoe, Dzhanikoy), as well as a series from Chongar Peninsula more or less peculiar morphologically, but preliminarily are identified here as *D. c. panticapaeum*.

The population from Taman Peninsula is strongly isolated from Crimea populations by Strait of Kerch, but specimens from that population demonstrate no distinguishing characters from Crimea populations. So, now Taman population is included in *D. c. panticapaeum*.

A small, strange paratype male (MD) of *D. c. gorodinskii* from Perekop Isthmus [„Kherson, Turetsky Val, 4.1982“] is also regarded here as *D. c. panticapaeum*.

15. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium sindorum* ssp. nov.

(Figs 54-55)

Type locality. Krasnodar reg., Anapa environs.

Type material. Holotype (♂): with two labels: 1) “Anapa 20.iv.1918 D.Zavileisky“, 2) “*Dorcadion sulcipenne* Kr. Vorišek det. 1975“ - MD. Paratypes: (1 ♀): Kavk., Anapa, iv.1919, Arnoldi - MD; (11 ♂♂, 13 ♀♀): Novorossiysk - ZIN.

Diagnosis. Body moderately big; antennae black with dark-red 1st joint, which can be sometimes nearly black or rather light; prothorax lateral tubercles well developed, shortly angulated, sometimes a little sharpened; pronotal longitudinal furrow in males usually shallow; pronotal longitudinal stripes very narrow, but distinct; pronotum usually with moderately sparse big dots and fine dense punctation; males pronotal black pubescence distinct; male elytra densely covered with black pubescence; females always autochromal with densely pubescent dark or sometimes pale elytra; dorsal pale stripes usually diffused or sometimes rather contrast, with or without black spots; humeral pale stripes in females also can be indistinct; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) usually more or less

Figs 44-53. *D. c. panticapaeum* Plavilstshikov, 1951:
 44- male, Kazantip; 45- female, same locality; 46-
 male, Bagerovo; 47- female, same locality; 48- male,
 Dzhankoy; 49- male, Uytuoec; 50- male, Oktyabr,
 Pyatikhatka River; 51- male, Kherson Region, Chongar;
 52- female, same locality; 53- male, Turetskiy Val.

Figs 54-55. *D. c. sindorum* sp. nov.: 54- Holotype, male, Anapa (present designation); 55- Paratype, female, same locality (present designation).

Figs 56-57. *D. c. bartenevi* sp. nov.: 56- Holotype, male, Tarkhankut peninsula (present designation); 57- Paratype, female, Tarkhankut peninsula, Olenovka (present designation).

Figs 58-63. *D. c. gorodinskii* Danilevsky, 1996: 58 - Holotype, male, Kherson Region, Rybalche; 59- Paratype, female, same locality; 60- female, same locality; 61-62- male, Odessa Region, Khadzhibeevskiy Liman; 63- female, Odessa environs.

developed, but sometimes totally obliterated; anterior part of humeral area with several big dots disappearing before middle; fine elytral irregular striae usually distinct; apical elytral margin usually reddish; legs red or dark-red.

Body length in males: 11.7-13.0 mm, in females: 11.6-14.0 mm; body width in males: 4.1-4.7 mm, in females: 4.8-5.6 mm.

The new subspecies differs from closely related *D. c. panticapaeum* by bigger size, better developed prothoracic tubercles and domination of dark pubescence in females.

Distribution. South-West Krasnodar Region: Anapa environs / MD; most probably low hills and planes to about Novorossiysk environs - ZIN.

Remarks. A big series of specimens (11 ♂♂, 13 ♀♀ - ZIN) with the label “Novorossiysk” are just same morphologically as a pair with the label “Anapa”, so most probably all the beetles belong to one population from the hilly plane area between Anapa and Novorossiysk.

Etymology. The name of the new subspecies is created on the base of the name of ancient people of the region - Sindi (Sinds) - Greek: Σινδοί.

16. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium bartenevi* ssp. nov.

(Figs 56-57)

Type locality. Ukraine: cape Tarkhankut, the most western part of Crimea Peninsula.

Type material. Holotype (♂): Crimea, Tarkhankut peninsula, 2.vi.85, I.Plyushch - MD. Paratypes: (2 ♂): Tarkhankut peninsula, Olenevka, 20.iv.1952, 10.v.1952, I.Maltsev - AB, ZMM; (1 ♀): same locality, 11.vi.1970 - AB.

Diagnosis. Only 3 males and 1 female available; body small; antennae black with dark-red 1st joint; prothorax lateral tubercles angulated and a little attenuated; pronotal longitudinal furrow distinct, not interrupted; pronotal longitudinal stripes in males relatively wide; pronotum with moderately sparse big dots and fine dense punctation, with recumbent black pubescence; elytra in males densely covered with black pubescence; females autochromal, with elytra densely covered by pale-brown pubescence; pale dorsal stripes in a single known female diffused; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) well developed anteriorly; anterior part of humeral area with several big dots disappearing before middle; fine elytral irregular striae indistinct; apical elytral margin usually reddish; legs dark-red.

Body length in males: 10.5-12.3 mm, in females: 10.2 mm; body width in males: 3.5-4.3 mm, in females: 4.2 mm.

D. c. bartenevi ssp. nov. differs from the closest *D. c. panticapaeum* by very distinct pronotal punctation and better developed lateral thoracic tubercles.

Distribution. Only one population known: cape Tarkhankut, the most western part of Crimean Peninsula - MD, AB.

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to well known specialist in Ukrainian Cerambycidae Alexandr Fedorovitch Bartenev (Kharkov), who studied Cerambycidae of Crimean Peninsula for many years.

17. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium gorodinskii* Danilevsky, 1996
(Figs 58-63)

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium gorodinskii Danilevsky, 1996: 65 ("South Ukraine, Kherson environs, Rybalche"; "Kherson environs, Turetsky Val."); Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 33; Bartenev, 2004: 37; 2009: 301.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium gorodinskii, Danilevsky et al., 2005: 137; Danilevsky, 2010a: 245.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium cinerarium, Bartenev, 2009: 300 part.

Type locality. South Ukraine, Kherson Region, Rybalche - according to the original description.

Type material. Holotype (♂): with two labels: 1) "Kherson reg., Rybalche, 28.iv-10.v.95, S.Vaschenko"; 2) "Holotypus, *Dorcadion cinerarium gorodinskii* ssp. nov., det. M.Danilevsky, 1996" [red] - MD. Paratypes: (2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀): same locality - MD; (1 ♂): same locality - ZIN; (1 ♀): same locality, 09.v.1983 - ZIN; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, same locality, 17.v.1994, P.Udovichenko - MPSU; (5 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀): same locality, 05.iv-03.v.1996, 15.iv-03.v.1996, S.Vaschenko - MD, ML; (1 ♂): Kherson reg. - ZIN; (1 ♂): Kherson, Nikolaevsk, 1901, G.Suvorov - ZIN; (1 ♂): Kherson, Znamenka, [Belozerka District], 26.vi.1906, K. Yatsentkovskiy - ZIN; (1 ♀): Kherson, Dorevka, 24.iv.1915 - ZIN; (2 ♂♂): Odessa - ZIN; (3 ♂♂): same locality, 02.iii.1906, 20.iv.1908, Yatsentkovskiy - ZIN; (5 ♀♀): same locality, 22.iii.1921, 30.iii.1921, 15.iv.1921, D. Znoyko - ZIN; (11 ♂, 5 ♀): same locality, 09.v.1937, 12.v.1938 - ZMM; (2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀): Odessa, Khadzhibeevskiy Liman, 05.v.1921, 10.v.1921, 30.viii.1921 - ZIN; (1 ♂): Odessa, same locality, 08.v.1961, I.Yasolnev - AB; (1 ♂): Odessa, Malaya Severinovka, 14.iv.1927 - ZIN; (1 ♀): Nikolaev environs, v.1977 - MD; (7 ♂♂, 1 ♀): Purkary, Akkerman reg., 09-14.iv.1911, Chernavin - ZIN; (1 ♂): Novaya Bogdanovka, Bug Liman, 16.v.1978, V.Odnosum leg. - MD; (2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀): Nikolaev District, Parytino, 26.iv.1997, S.Vashchenko - MD.

Diagnosis. Body relatively big; antennae black with dark-red 1st joint, which can be sometimes nearly black; prothorax lateral tubercles well developed, often sharpened and curved backwards, rarely obtuse; pronotal longitudinal furrow in males usually distinct; pronotal longitudinal stripes narrow but always distinct; pronotum with moderately dense big dots and fine dense punctation; sometimes pronotal punctation rather rough with conjugated dots; males pronotal black pubescence distinct; male elytra densely covered with black pubescence, rudiments of pale humeral stripes in males often well developed; females always autochromal with densely pubescent pale elytra; dorsal pale stripes usually diffused or sometimes rather contrast, with or without black spots; longitudinal elytral sculpture (furrows and carinae) usually more or less developed; anterior part of humeral area with numerous big dots usually distributed beyond middle; fine elytral irregular striae well developed, but usually indistinct under dense pubescence; apical elytral margin usually reddish; legs red or dark-red.

Body length in males: 9.3-13.3 mm, in females: 10.7-15.5 mm; body width in males: 3.2-4.8 mm, in females: 4.3-6.5 mm.

D. c. gorodinskii differs from the eastern *D. c. panticapaeum* by big size, well developed prothoracic tubercles, rough pronotal and elytral punctation.

Distribution. South of Moldova and South Ukraine from Odessa environs to Kherson Region and to the west of Zaporozhye Region; several localities are known Purkary [46°32'N, 29°51'E] in Moldova - ZIN; Odessa Region: Odessa environs - ZIN, ZMM; Khadzhibeevskiy Liman, 46°51'N, 30°28'E - ZIN, AB; north of Kuyalnitskiy Liman - (Bartenev, 2009); Nikolaevskiy Region: Nikolaev environs - MD; Nikolaev District, Staraya Bogdanovka environs [46°50'N, 31°54'E], Dnepr-Bug Liman - (Bartenev, 2009); Novaya Bogdanovka, Bug Liman - MD; Nikolaev District, Parutino - MD; Kherson Region: Rybalche - MPSU,

MD, ML; Darevka near Kherson-city - ZIN; Belozerka District, Znamenka, 46°42'N, 32°23'E - ZIN; Zaporozhye Region: Khortitsa Island [47°49'N, 35°05'E] - (Danilevsky, 2010b); Kamenka Dnepropetrovskaya [47°29'N, 34°23'E], in about 70km SW Zaporozhye - (Danilevsky, 2010b).

Most probably, localities mentioned by Bartenev (2009) as Burkuty and Potievskiy area of Tchernomorsky Natural Reserve (both in Kherson Region, Golaya Pristan District) also belong to *D.c.gorodinskii*.

Remarks. The paratype male (MD) published as „Kherson environs, Turetsky Val, 4.1982“ has in fact another label: „Kherson, Turetsky Val, 4.1982“, so it is not the environs of the city, but the area near Perekop. The beetle is very small (9.0 mm), with rather narrow sutural white stripe and short thoracic lateral tubercles. It is identified here as *D. c. panticapaeum*.

CONCLUSIONS

All the 17 subspecies can be morphologically divided in 2 groups: *D. c. cinerarium*- group (with glabrous males) and *D. c. panticapaeum*-group (with pubescent males).

Each subspecies is independently locally developed from a mutual widely distributed ancestor. Each one is genetically closer to its nearest geographical neighbours, and then to the distant subspecies of same group. So, each morphological group (or subgroup) of subspecies is artificial and the phylogenetic scheme of the genus evolution looks like a net, but not like a tree.

The mutual ancestor of all the subspecies most probably had glabrous elytra in males as most of *Dorcadion* species close to *D. cinerarium* in Europe and Caucasus (*D. pedestre*, *D. lineatocolle*, *D. sisianense*, *D. megriense*, *D. kasikoporanum*, *D. shushense*, *D. caspiense*, *D. micans*) has glabrous male elytra. Closely related species to *D. cinerarium* with pubescent males are distributed only in Transcaucasia and Turkey (*D. sulcipenne*, *D. argonauta*, *D. demokidovi*, *D. maljushenkoi*, *D. czegodaevi*).

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REFERENCES

ALTHOFF J. & DANILEVSKY M. L. 1997: *A check-list of Longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycoidea) of Europe*. Ljubljana: Slovinsko Entomolosko Drustvo Stefana Michielija: 64 pp.

- AURIVILLIUS C. 1922: Cerambycidae: Lamiinae I. Pars 73. In: SCHENKLING S. (ed.). *Coleopterorum Catalogus. Volumen XXIII. Cerambycidae II*. [1921]. Berlin: W. Junk, 322 pp
- BARTENEV A. F. 2004: A review of the long-horned beetles species (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of the fauna of Ukraine. *Izvestiya Kharkovskogo Entomologicheskogo Obshchestva [The Kharkov Entomological Society Gazette]* 2003 (2004), 11(1-2): 24-43. [in Russian]
- BARTENEV A. F. 2009: *Longicorn-beetles of Left-Bank Ukraine and Crimea*. Kharkov: Kharkov National University: 405 pp. [in Russian]
- BREUNING E. 1946: Nouvelles formes de *Dorcadion* (Col., Cerambycidae). *Miscellanea Entomologica* 43: 93-132.
- BREUNING S. 1956: Quelques nouvelles formes du genre *Dorcadion* Dalm. *Longicornia* 3: 723-728.
- BREUNING S. 1958: *Catalogue des Lamiaires du Monde (Col., Céramb.)*. 1. Lief. Munchen: Im Verlag des Museums G. Frey: 1-48 pp.
- BREUNING S. 1962: Revision der Dorcadionini (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). *Entomologische Abhandlungen und Berichte aus dem Staatlichen Museum für Tierkunde in Dresden* 27: 1-665.
- CHYUBCHIK V. YU. 2010: The annotated list of longicorn-beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of the Central Moldova. *Russian Entomological Journal* 19(2): 111-118.
- DANILEVSKY M. L. 1996a: New Longicorn Beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from South East Europe. *Russian Entomological Journal* 4 (1995), 1-4: 63-66.
- DANILEVSKY M. L. 1996b: New taxa of the genus *Dorcadion* Dalman from Asia (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). *Lambillionea*, 96, 2(2): 407-420.
- DANILEVSKY M. L. 2010a: Tribe Dorcadionini, pp. 241-264. In: LÖBL I. & SMETANA A. (ed.): *Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, Vol. 6*. Stenstrup: Apollo Books: 924 pp.
- DANILEVSKY M. L. 2010b: www.cerambycidae.net
- DANILEVSKY M. L. KASATKIN D. G. & RUBENYAN A. A. 2005: Revision of the taxonomic structure of the tribe Dorcadionini (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) on the base of endophallic morphology. *Russian Entomological Journal*, 13(2004), 3: 127-149.
- DANILEVSKY M. L. & MIROSHNIKOV A. I. 1985: *Timber-Beetles of Caucasus (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)*. Key. Krasnodar: 419 pp. [in Russian]
- FABRICIUS J. C. 1787: *Mantissa insectorum, sistens eorum species nuper detectas adiectis characteribus genericis, differentiis specificis, emendationibus, observationibus. Tomus I. Hafniae*: C. G. Proft: xx + 348 pp.
- FISCHER VON WALDHEIM G. Nouvelles espèces d'Insectes de la Russie, décrites par G. Fischer. *Journal de la Société des Naturalistes de l'Université Impériale de Moscou. Première Année. No I e II, Avec 3 Figures*. Moscou: Imprimé chez C.F. Schildbach: 12-18.
- GANGLBAUER L. 1884: Bestimmungstabellen europäischer Coleopteren: VIII. Cerambycidae. Schluss. Mit Berücksichtigung der Formen Algiers und des paläarktischen Asiens, exclusive jener von Japan. *Verhandlungen der Kaiserlich-Königlichen Zoologisch-Botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien* 33 [1883]: 437-586.
- ICZN 1999: *International Code of Zoological Nomenclature*. Fourth Edition. International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature. Published by The International Trust for Zoological Nomenclature: 306 pp.
- KALIUZHNYAYA N. S., KOMAROV E. V. & CHEREZOVA L. B. 2000: *Coleoptera of lower Volga river*. Volgograd: 204 pp. [in Russian]
- KASATKIN D. G. & ARZANOV YU. G. 1997: Der Bockkaffer (Cerambycidae). Material für fauna der Kaffer (Coleoptera) norden Kaukasus und untere Don. *Records of Kharkov Entomological Society* 5(2): 63-70.
- KRAATZ G. 1873a: *Dorcadion sericatum*, Kraatz. In: KÜSTER H. C. 1873: *Die Käfer Europa's. Nach der Natur beschrieben von Dr. G. Kraatz im Anschluss an die Käfer Europa's von Dr. H.C. Küster*. XXIX. Heft. Bauer & Raspe in Nürnberg: 98.
- KRAATZ G. 1873b: *Dorcadion macropus*, Kraatz. In: KÜSTER H. C. 1873: *Die Käfer Europa's. Nach der Natur beschrieben von Dr. G. Kraatz im Anschluss an die Käfer Europa's von Dr. H. C. Küster*. XXIX. Heft. Bauer & Raspe in Nürnberg: 99.
- KRYNICKI J. 1832: Enumeratio Coleopterorum Rossiae meridionalis et praecipue in Universitatis Caesareae Charkoviensis circulo obvenientium, quae annorum 1827-1831 spatio observavit, P. P. E. Ioannes Krynicki. *Bulletin de la Societe Imperiale des Naturalistes de Moscou* 5: 65-179, pis II-III.
- KÜSTER H. C. 1847a: *Dorcadion sulcipenne*, Küster. *Die Käfer Europa's. Nach der Natur beschrieben von Dr. H. C. Küster. Mit Beiträgen mehrerer Entomologen*. VIII. Heft. Bauer & Raspe in Nürnberg: 87.
- KÜSTER H. C. 1847b: *Dorcadion pusillum*, Besser. *Die Käfer Europa's. Nach der Natur beschrieben von Dr. H. C. Küster. Mit Beiträgen mehrerer Entomologen*. VIII. Heft. Bauer & Raspe in Nürnberg: 90.

- KÜSTER H. C. 1847c: *Dorcadion caucasicum*, Sturm. Die Käfer Europa's. Nach der Natur beschrieben von Dr. H. C. Küster. Mit Beiträgen mehrerer Entomologen. X. Heft. Bauer & Raspe in Nürnberg: 98.
- KÜSTER H. C. 1848: *Dorcadion cinerarium*, Fabricius. Die Käfer Europa's. Nach der Natur beschrieben von Dr. H. C. Küster. Mit Beiträgen mehrerer Entomologen. XV. Heft. Bauer & Raspe in Nürnberg: 78.
- LAZAREV M. A. 2009: Armenian *Dorcadion* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of "cinerarium-group". *Studies and reports of District Museum Prague-East. Taxonomical Series* 5(1-2): 197-220.
- LAZAREV M. A. 2010: New species of genus *Dorcadion* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from Transcaucasia. *Eversmannia, Entomological Research in the Russia and Adjacent Regions* 21-22: 3-5, 1 pl.
- LOBANOV A. L., DANILEVSKY M. L. & MURZIN S. V. 1982: Systematic list of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of the USSR. 2. *Revue d'Entomologie* 61(2): 252-277.
- MARTYNOV V. V. & PISARENKO T. A. 2004: A review of the fauna and ecology of the long-horned beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of southeast Ukraine. *The Kharkov Entomological Society Gazette* 2003(2004), 11(1-2): 44-69. [in Russian]
- MEDVEDEV S. I. 1950: Preliminary results of the study of entomofauna of "Provalskaya Steppe" of Vorosholovgrad region. *Scientific Notes of Kharkov University. Trudy NII Biologii* 14-15: 89-109. [in Russian]
- MEDVEDEV S. I. & SHAPIRO D. S. 1957: To the study of beetle (Coleoptera) fauna of Moldavian SSR and neighbour Ukraine regions. *Archives of Science and Research Institute of Biology and Biological Faculty of Kharkov A.M. Gorky University* 30:173-206 [in Russian].
- MILLER E. & ZUBOWSKY N. 1906: II. Materialien zu Kenntniss der entomologischen Fauna Bessarabiens. *Travaux de la société des Naturalistes et des Amateurs des sciences naturelles de Bessarabie*, 1(1) (1904-1906): 57-70.
- MILLER E. & ZUBOWSKY N. 1910: V. Materialien zu Kenntniss der entomologischen Fauna Bessarabiens. *Travaux de la société des Naturalistes et des Amateurs des sciences naturelles de Bessarabie*, 2 (1908-1909): 31-150.
- MILLER E. & ZUBOWSKY N. 1917: VI. Materialien zu Kenntniss der entomologischen Fauna Bessarabiens. *Travaux de la société des Naturalistes et des Amateurs des sciences naturelles de Bessarabie*, (1914-1915): 119-150.
- MIROSHNIKOV A. I. 2004: To the knowledge of timber-beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of Caucasus. *Actual Questions of Plant Protection, Agrochemistry, Agrosoilstudy and Insect Fauna in Krasnodar Region. Transactions of Kuban State Agricultural University* 409(437): 133-138. [in Russian]
- NEGROBOV S. O., TZURIKOV M. N., LOGVINOVSKY V. D., FOMICHEV A. I., PROKIN A. A. & GILMUTDINOV K. S. 2005: Order Coleoptera. *Cadastré of Invertebrata of Voronezh region. Voronezh*: 534-673. [in Russian]
- OGLOBLIN D. A. 1948: 73. Fam. Cerambycidae / Timber Beetles or Longhorned Beetles. In: *A Key of the Insects of the European Part of the USSR*. Moscow-Leningrad: 450-471 [in Russian]
- ÖZDIKMEN H. 2007: The Longicorn beetles of Turkey (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). Part. 1. Black Sea region. *Munis Entomology & Zoology* 2(2): 179-422.
- ÖZDIKMEN H. 2010: The Turkish Dorcadiini with zoogeographical remarks (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lamiinae). *Munis Entomology & Zoology* 5(2): 380-498.
- PALLAS P. S. 1781: *Icones insectorum praesertim Rossiae Sibiriaque peculiarium quae collegit et descriptionibus illustravit Petrus Simon Pallas*. Erlangae: Sumtu Wolfgangi Waltheri: 1-104, 8 ill.
- PERISSINOTTO A. & LUCHINI S. R. 1966: Coleotteri Raccolti Nel Vicino e Medio Oriente Nota I. *Dorcadion* Dalm. (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). *Bollettino della Societa Entomologica Italiana* 96(9-10): 147-149.
- PIC M. 1901: Descriptions. Pp. 9-14. *Matériaux pour servir à l'étude des longicornes. 3ème cahier, 3ème partie*. Lyon: Imprimerie Jacquet Frères: 32 pp.
- PIC M. 1942: *Opuscula martialis* VII. *L'Échange, Revue Linnéenne. Numéro Spécial* 7: 1-16.
- PLAVILSTSHIKOV N. N. 1927a: Notes on timber-beetles of Caucasus. II. (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). *Records of Stavropol Entomological Society*, III(1): 1-7. [in Russian]
- PLAVILSTSHIKOV N. N. 1927b: Addenda et corrigenda concernant le Coleopterorum Catalogus, parties 73 et 74 (Lamiinae) de Chr. Aurivillius. *Encyclopédie Entomologique (Paris) Ser. B. I. Col. 2*: 49-68.
- PLAVILSTSHIKOV N. N. 1931: Beitrag zur Verbreitung der paläarktischen Cerambyciden. II. *Entomologisches Nachrichtenblatt* 5(3): 71-76.
- PLAVILSTSHIKOV N. N. 1932a: *Dorcadion*-Studien II (Col., Cerambycidae). *Entomologische Blätter* 28: 181-184.
- PLAVILSTSHIKOV N. N. 1932b: *Timber-beetles - Timber Pests*. Moscow, Leningrad: 200 pp. [in Russian]
- PLAVILSTSHIKOV N. N. 1948: *A Key for Longicorn Beetles of Armenia*. Erevan: 232 pp. [in Russian]
- PLAVILSTSHIKOV N. N. 1951: New species of Timber-Beetles of Palaeartic fauna (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). *Sbornik trudov Zoologicheskogo Muzeya MGU* 7: 113-122. [in Russian]
- PLAVILSTSHIKOV N. N. 1958: *Faune de l'URSS. Insectes Coléptères. V.23 (1). Cerambycidae (P.3). Sous-famille Lamiinae, p.1*. Moscou, Leningrad: 592 pp. [in Russian]

- PLAVILSTSHIKOV N. N. 1965: 75-th Fam. Cerambycidae - Timber Beetles, Longicornes. In: *A Key to Insects of the European Part of the USSR*, v. 2, *Coleoptera and Strepsiptera*. Moscow-Leningrad : "Nauka": 389-419. [in Russian]
- PRISNYI A. V. & VOROBIEVA. O. V. 2005: *Scientific collection funds of "Museum of Zoology" at the chair of zoology and ecology of Belgorod State University. Issue 1. Insects - Ectognatha. Beetles - Coleoptera*. Belgorod: IPC "POLITERRA": 63pp. [in Russian]
- STURM J. 1843: *Catalog der Käfer-Sammlung von Jacob Sturm*. Nürnberg: J. Sturm: xii + 386 pp. + 6 pls.
- THOMSON J. 1867: D'une classification nouvelles de la famille des Cérambycides (Insectes, Coléoptères). *Physis. Recueil d'Histoire Naturelle* 1: 1-128.
- WINKLER A. 1929: Cerambycidae. In: *Catalogus Coleopterorum regionis palaearcticae*. Wien : Wenkler et Wagner: 1135-1226.
- ZAHAIKEVITCH I. K. 1991: *Taxonomy and Ecology of Longicorn Beetles*. Kiev. "Naukova Dumka": 180 pp. [in Russian]

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